

**Horizon Europe (HORIZON)
Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
Doctoral Networks (MSCA-DN)**

ANNEX 1

Description of the action (DoA)

Part B

101120360 – SHARE-CTD

HORIZON – MSCA – 2023 – DN

Sharing and re-using clinical trial data to maximise impact

History of changes

1. Indicators for the verification and measurement of the research to be carried out are not clearly articulated.

We wrote: *The TAC will monitor ESR's progress (regarding the ESR specific deliverables) as frequent as necessary (at least twice a year) and report the meeting minutes and updated CDPs and RPs to the SB. The SB will evaluate the overall role of the ongoing individual ESR project regarding the general SHARE-CTD perspective and will give feedback.* Additionally, for each individual ESR Table 3.1.f lists expected results which guide the evaluation process of the TAB and SB. These individual deliverables provide in the tools for the verification and measurement of the individual research progress and its evaluation regarding the overall goals of the networks. Furthermore, there are deliverables which provide network wide summaries of the results. The Working Group Scientific Input will coordinate and supervise these interdependent common activities and will report the results to the SB.

2. Roles of partners from the academic and non-academic sector:

The following table shows the teaching tasks and secondment opportunities provided by the associated partners. The rows presenting non-academic partners have a grey background. Specific modifications in the text are made in the specific section.

Associated partner	Teachnig tasks	Secondments
University of Zurich	Propaedeutic training (M10); Organising schooling event (1) M13;	ESR 11 (M17-M22)
Centre for Journalology	Schooling event (3) Conference	ESR 2 (M23-M34)
METRICS	Schooling event (3) Conference	ESR 8 (M17-M22) ESR 10 (M26 – M31)
YODA	Datathon (1) – (3)	ESR 1 (M36-M38) ESR 6 (M38-M43)
ECRIN-ERIC	Schooling events (1) Professional Training (2)	ESR 1 (M27-M29) ESR 7 (M29-M35) ESR 11 (M26-M31)
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam		ESR 6 (M26-M31)
Bayer AG	Schooling event (2); Professional Training (1) – (2);	ESR 1 (M18-M20) ESR 3 (M20-M22) ESR 8 (M35-M37) ESR 9 (M26-M27; M38)
SciCrunch Inc	Schooling Event (3)	ESR 4 (M17-M21)
Information Centre for Life Sciences	Datathon (1) – (3); Schooling event (1)	ESR 5 (M17-M19) ESR 7 (M15-M17)
National Institute for Health and Care Excellence	Professional Training (3) Schooling event (2)	ESR 8 (M26-M28)
German Institute of Human Nutrition	Schooling event (1) Professional Training (3)	ESR 3 (M32-M34) ESR 5 (M29-M34)
Smart Data Analysis and Statistics	Schooling event (2); Datathon (2) Professional Training (3)	ESR 9 (M17; M41)
L'organisation pour une recherche Inserm éthique et responsable	Schooling event (2); Professional Training (2)	

3. In Table 3.1.e the planned start for all ESRs is set to month 10
4. The timeframe is adjusted Table 3.1.f: Individual research projects.

5. Estimates regarding the number of persons participating in surveys and interviews are added to the projects of ESR:

- ESR 2: Survey mentioned is literature and website based and uses digital search strategies.
- ESR 6 and ESR 7: Numbers added in Table 3.1.f

Table of Contents

1	LIST OF PARTICIPATING ORGANISATIONS.....	5
2	EXCELLENCE	7
2.1	Quality and pertinence of the project’s research and innovation objectives (and the extent to which they are ambitious, and go beyond the state of the art).....	7
2.2	Soundness of the proposed methodology (including interdisciplinary approaches, consideration of the gender dimension and other diversity aspects if relevant for the research project, and the quality and appropriateness of open science practices)	11
1.1	Quality and credibility of the training programme (including transferable skills, inter/multidisciplinary, inter-sectoral and gender as well as other diversity aspects)	16
2.3	Quality of the supervision (including mandatory joint supervision for industrial and joint doctorate projects).....	20
3	IMPACT.....	22
3.1	Contribution to structuring doctoral training at the European level and to strengthening European innovation capacity, including the potential for:	23
3.2	Credibility of the measures to enhance the career perspectives and employability of researchers and contribution to their skills development	24
3.3	Suitability and quality of the measures to maximise expected outcomes and impacts, as set out in the dissemination and exploitation plan, including communication activities.....	25
3.4	The magnitude and importance of the project’s contribution to the expected scientific, societal and economic impacts (project’s pathways towards impact)	27
4	QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY OF THE IMPLEMENTATION.....	29
4.1	Quality and effectiveness of the work plan, assessment of risks and appropriateness of the effort assigned to work packages	29
4.2	Quality, capacity and role of each participant, including hosting arrangements and extent to which the consortium as a whole brings together the necessary expertise	39
5	ETHICS ISSUES.....	41

1 LIST OF PARTICIPATING ORGANISATIONS

Consortium Member	Legal Entity Short Name	Academic	Non-academic	Awards Doctoral Degrees	Country	Dept./ Division / Laboratory	Scientist -in-Charge	Role of associated Partner or link to beneficiary
<u>Beneficiaries</u>								
Ludwig-Maximilian-University	LMU	X		PhD	Germany	IBE	UM	
University of Rennes 1	UR1	X		PhD	France	IRSET	FN, CL	
Berlin Institute of Health @ Charité	Charité	X		PhD	Germany	BIH	FP, TW	
University Medical Center Göttingen	UMG	X			Germany	DMI	US	
Medical University of Vienna	MUW	X		PhD	Austria	CeMSIIS	MP	
University of Padova	UPD	X		PhD	Italy	DGP	IC	
Hospices Civils de Lyon	HCL	X			France	SREC	ED	
UMC Utrecht	UMCU	X			Netherlands	JC	VJ	

<u>Associated Partners</u>								
University of Zurich	UZH	X		PhD	Switzerland	DB	LH	TC, ESR
Centre for Journalology	CFJ	X			Canada		DM	TC, S
METRICS	METRICS	X			United States		Jl	TC, S
YODA	YODA	X			United States		JR	TC, S
ECRIN-ERIC	ECRIN		X		France		CK, CO	TC, S
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	VUA	X			Netherlands	FBMS	EK	S
Bayer AG	BAYER		X		Germany		CG	TC, S
SciCrunch Inc	SCr		X		United States		AB	TC, S
Information Centre for Life Sciences	ZB MED		X		Germany		JF	TC, S
National Institute for Health and Care Excellence	NICE		X		United Kingdom		DD	TC, S
German Institute of Human Nutrition	DIfE		X		Germany		MS	TC, S
Smart Data Analysis and Statistics	SDAaS		X		Netherlands		TD	TC, S
L'organisation pour une recherche Inserm éthique et responsable	LORIER		X		France		PR	TC

Associated Partners linked to a beneficiary								
University Claude Bernard Lyon 1	UCBL	X		PhD	France		FF	TC
Utrecht University	UU	X		PhD	Netherlands		AP	TC
Georg-August University Göttingen	UGOE	X		PhD	Germany		AT	TC

Persons: UM: Ulrich Mansmann; FN: Florian Naudet; CL: Clara Locher; FP: Fabian Prasser; TW: Tracey Weissgerber; US: Ulrich Sax; MP: Martin Posch; IC: Ioana Cristea; ED: Evelyne Decullier; VJ: Valentijn M.T. de Jong; LH: Leonhard Held; DM: David Moher; JI: John Ioannidis; JR: Joseph S. Ross; CO: Christian Ohmann; CK: Christine Kubiak; EK: Eirini Karyotaki; CG: Christoph Gerlinger; AB: Anita Bandrowski; JF: Juliane Fluck; DD: Dalia Dawoud; MS: Matthias Schulze; TD: Thomas Debray; PR: Philippe Ravaud; FF: Prof. Dr. Frederic Fleury; Prof. Dr. Anton Pijpers; AT: Prof. Dr. Metin Tolan

Departments: IBE: Department of Medical Information Sciences, Biometry, and Epidemiology; IRSET: Clinical Investigation Center; BIH: Berlin Institute of Health; DMI: Department of Medical Informatics; CeMSIIS: Center for Medical Statistics, Informatics and Intelligent Systems; DGP: Department of General Psychology; SREC: Service Recherche et épidémiologie Clinique; JC: Julius Center for Health Sciences and Primary Care, Department of Epidemiology; DB: Department of Biostatistics; FBMS: Faculty of Behavioural and Movement Sciences

Roles: TC: Teaching Courses, S: Secondment, ESR: Early stage researcher

2 EXCELLENCE

2.1 Quality and pertinence of the project's research and innovation objectives (and the extent to which they are ambitious, and go beyond the state of the art)

Introduction: Clinical trial results are the source of foundational evidence for contemporary medical decision making. This evidence is widely used by regulatory bodies, health technology assessment agencies, and is considered the gold standard for assessing treatment effects. The value and trustworthiness of medical research may be enhanced by sharing of patient-level clinical trial data together with the code on which analyses are based^{1,2,3} as well as other materials such as the protocol, case report form, and data dictionary.

Keeping this background in mind, *clinical trial data sharing* (CTDS) offers unique opportunities for external re-analysis, which enables conclusions to be re-examined, verified or, occasionally, corrected, thereby building trust. CTDS also allows individual participant data (IPD) meta-analysis and other strategies that build upon previous data and code, such as secondary analyses and methodological work. CTDS should accelerate discovery, reduce false discovery rates, and potentially discourage misconduct and research waste, as well as allowing more value to be drawn from the original research investment. CTDS honours the generosity of clinical trial participants, because it maximises the utility of the data they provide⁴, and is widely viewed as a positive feature by stakeholders involved in clinical trials, including trial participants⁵.

CTDS experts are therefore urgently needed. A new generation of such experts can be nurtured by incorporating interdisciplinary methodological approaches to CTDS into curricula of existing medical PhD and Clinical Scientist programmes around the globe.

Figure 1: CTDS Principles

Organising *data sharing* (DS) activities both at the study level (e.g. requesting, preparing, sharing data and re-using the data) and at a global level (e.g. adopting and optimising data sharing policies) requires an inter- and transdisciplinary approach that includes clinical trials regulations, ethical, legal, and social issues, informatics, data science, biostatistics, and Meta Research, as well as domain expertise across different medical fields.

Those who establish best practice for clinical trial data need training in principles, governance, skills, and operations (see Figure 1). Such training should include best practices, measuring impact, and

practical exercises for the use of shared data. A coherent training curriculum should encompass the many topics related to best practices in CTDS.

¹ Koenig F, et al. (2015): Sharing clinical trial data on patient level: opportunities and challenges. DOI: 10.1002/bimj.201300283.

² Localio AR, et al. (2018): Statistical Code to Support the Scientific Story. DOI: 10.7326/M17-3431.

³ Mansmann U, et al (2023) Implementing clinical trial data sharing requires training a new generation of biomedical researchers, Nature Medicine (accepted, NMED-C120847B, https://cloud.ibe.med.uni-muenchen.de/umdtaiive2aiph3w/Paper_SHARE_CTD_final.pdf)

⁴ Taichman DB, et al. (2017): Data Sharing Statements for Clinical Trials: A Requirement of the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1002315.

⁵ Mello MM, et al. (2018): Clinical Trial Participants' Views of the Risks and Benefits of Data Sharing. DOI: 10.1056/NEJMsa1713258.

Best practice in preparing data for sharing requires standards (FAIR^{6,7} and TRUST Data Principles⁸), privacy protection of trial participants, efficient anonymisation, reporting of studies, and governance processes to access data⁹. Best practice in re-using a shared data set include the access and utilization of data and requires skills in handling data formats, managing deployment processes (e.g. data sharing platforms such as YODA¹⁰ or federated and distributed analyses that are needed when data cannot leave the host institution), implementing secondary studies such as IPD meta-analysis^{11,12}, clinical trial planning and biostatistical methods development. Obviously, skills in Open Science and reproducible research practices are paramount. Transparent reporting is needed to ensure that results can be properly interpreted and reproduced. Scientists with awareness of these topics and willingness to collaborate with the right experts are needed for a successful project set-up

Objectives: The research and curriculum proposed by SHARE-CTD (Sharing and re-using clinical trial data to maximise impact) intend to enable early stage researchers (ESRs) to explore pressing questions around CTDS and to gain deep insight into related practice. Their research will be embedded and supported by a training programme based on theory, practice and experience. It will allow a profound interaction with a wide range of experts as well as problem-based interactive methods such as datathons¹³ that promote transparency, honesty and collaboration. ESRs who complete the programme will know how to perform research to advance best practices for CTDS, and how to perform DS with a high level of professionalism. They will be able to address the following important issues: 1) enhancing public access to clinical study information, 2) reaffirming commitments to publish clinical trial results, 3) sharing results with patients who participate in clinical trials, 4) certifying procedures for sharing clinical trial information, and 5) enhancing DS with clinical researchers¹⁴.

Overview of the research programme: Eleven ESRs (See Table 3.1 e) from nine academic institutions will perform individual research and participate in three collaborative datathon projects. They will do research on problems related to preparing data for sharing as well as using shared data. Some will develop and assess technical as well as methodological topics. Others will get in contact with stakeholders and patients and perform surveys

⁶ Gouthamchand V, et al. (2021): FAIR-IFICATION OF STRUCTURED CLINICAL DATA. DOI: 10.1101/2021.07.23.21261032.

⁷ Wilkinson MD, et al. (2016): The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. DOI: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18.

⁸ Lin D, et al. (2020): The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. DOI: 10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7.

⁹ Sudlow R, et al. (2016): EFSPI/PSI working group on DS: accessing and working with pharmaceutical clinical trial patient level datasets - a primer for academic researchers. DOI: 10.1186/s12874-016-0171-x.

¹⁰ <https://yoda.yale.edu/> [08.11.2022].

¹¹ Tierney JF, et al. (2015): Individual Participant Data (IPD) Meta-analyses of Randomised Controlled Trials: Guidance on Their Use. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1001855.

¹² Debray TP, et al. (2015): Individual participant data (IPD) meta-analyses of diagnostic and prognostic modelling studies: guidance on their use. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1001886.

¹³ A datathon is an intense workshop that asks participants to utilise the data provided to develop and answer topic-driven questions or to develop innovative approaches to analyse the data

¹⁴ Zarin DA, Tse T (2016): Sharing Individual Participant Data (IPD) within the Context of the Trial Reporting System (TRS). DOI: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1001946.

among them. Some will be engaged in Meta Research. The datathons will provide increasing complexity: D1 will focus on reproducibility of a single trial, D2 will set the stage for an IPD meta-analysis. D3 will be a secondary use project and will allow the ESRs to apply the new competencies in full extend to a relevant research question. Figure 2 sketches the four objectives with corresponding research activities and how they are applied in three network-based datathons.

(1) Best practice in preparing data for sharing – ESR5 will do her/his research in FAIRification of clinical trials data and give respective input to the datathons. ESR3 will work on privacy protection of trial subjects and efficient anonymisation of their data. How this may affect protocols of future trials and define aspects of best practice in CTDS is a subtopic of ESR 11. As cooperative work, we will analyse governing processes to access data.

(2) Best practice in using shared data – ESR1 will work on topics of generalisability of treatment effects and validation of prognostic and predictive rules. Her/his work explores innovative strategies to assess the generalisability of a finding by showing its validity over a wider range of settings beyond the horizon of the study performed. ESR8 and ESR9 will concentrate on individual patient data meta-analysis, and on synthesis of randomized and non-randomized data. ESR10 will use IPD to formulate strategies against bias in meta-analyses¹⁵. ESR8 and ESR10 will focus on methodological aspects of IPDMA (Individual Patient Data Meta-Analysis). They will develop and assess methodologies for combining (patient-level and/or summary) data from randomised and non-randomised studies. All of this will be relevant in the second datathon (D2).

(3) Measuring impact in preparing data for sharing will use a wide range of Meta Research methodology (e.g. umbrella reviews, surveys, observational studies, simulations, etc.) and build on indicators of transparency, openness, and reproducibility for clinical trials. ESR4 will work on automated tools to monitor CTDS in the literature. Her/his results will be integrated into the ScreenIT pipeline¹⁶ (A set of automated tools that screen scientific papers for common problems). Applying this tool will allow the consortium to scale up its ability to analyse reporting practices in the medical literature. Additionally, a large-scale observational study looking at current DS policies in the leading biomedical journals (NEJM, The Lancet, JAMA, The BMJ, Annals of Internal Medicine, JAMA Internal Medicine, PLOS Medicine, BMC Medicine) provides relevant data. ESR2 will prepare and curate these data-sets for others to be reused. She/he will describe and compare *impact* over a five-years period using various outcomes between papers intending to share data and papers not intending to share data, adjusting on potential confounders. ESR7 will perform surveys and interviews to elucidate the patient perspective on CTDS. She/he will also results of ESR2 to see how the literature reflects handling of patient privacy.

(4) Measuring impact – using shared data will explore the impact of IPDMA in a case study in the field of mental health. ESR6 will perform a large-scale umbrella review of all relevant IPDMAs, describing their focus (e.g. efficacy, acceptability, safety, prognostic), indications, interventions, outcomes, as well as possible sources of biases (funding and financial COIs), publication of a protocol, rate of primary data recovery, involvement of professional statisticians, and overlap among topics and studies. She/he will use a meta-epidemiological approach to examine the role of DS by comparing estimates across meta-analyses from trials where investigators made data available and those where they did not. Finally, ESR6 will conduct a qualitative analysis using surveys and interviews with main authors of IPDMA to identify reasons for lack of participation, beyond what is reported in the paper. ESR11 surveys all pivotal trials in oncology submitted to the European Medicine

¹⁵ IPD meta-analyses (IPDMA) are a type of systematic review and evidence synthesis and allow scientists to answer crucial questions about treatment harms and personalisation (individualised medicine).

¹⁶ Weissgerber T, et al. (2021): Automated screening of COVID-19 preprints: can we help authors to improve transparency and reproducibility? DOI: 10.1038/s41591-020-01203-7.

Agency and reproduces their results on the main outcome(s) and safety results. Her/his results will allow to pilot-test a label “reproducible science” for reproducible trials, a potential new incentive for sponsors sharing their data leading to successful reproduction. This adds to one of the general goals of SHARE-CTD: to study the impact of DS practices on clinical research reproducibility and to explore potential pitfalls of data re-use (e.g. reproducibility issues associated with multiple testing, publication bias etc.).

Pertinence and innovative aspects of the research programme: Current DS policies in clinical medicine are (besides data from cohort studies) strongly focused on clinical trial data¹⁷, indicating that the scientific community recognises the importance of CTDS. CTDS strengthens the practice of medical research and the integrity of the clinical trial system¹⁸.

We explored the potential relevance of the SHARE-CTD project in a *scoping review* that retrieved research focusing on the impact of CTDS¹⁹. It concludes that there is a lack of methodology to evaluate impact of IPD sharing and consequently no clear evidence on its effect. This contributes to uncertainties in the implementation and adoption of existing DS policies. The scoping review also provides the empirical basis for the proposed research programme. It is necessary to understand the status quo and ongoing developments to avoid duplications of efforts and to waste resources²⁰.

Those advocating for DS face many challenges, including, scepticism from trialists²¹. There is a need to for high-level evidence (accepted, even valued by patients) demonstrating that the value of medical research increases with greater transparency, and with the opportunity for independent researchers to re-analyse, synthesise, or build on previous data. We therefore published a policy forum paper to PLOS Medicine detailing a research agenda dedicated to monitoring and optimising best practices to increase the value of shared data²². This paper is the starting point of the SHARE-CTD research programme. In spring 2023, Nature Medicine will publish the roadmap of our project as a comment paper in a series on *Evidence in Medicine* acknowledging its pertinence²³.

To our knowledge, this is the first research and training programme to explore and promote a cooperative, comprehensive, and practical DS framework with a specific emphasis on clinical trial data. Extensive teaching activities and on-line material regarding DS and CTDS are available. A comprehensive programme which integrates all aspects (see Figure 1) does not seem to exist.

Our proposal incorporates academic, public, and industrial partners. While pharmaceutical companies are actively practicing in CTDS²⁴, specific problems that they face include privacy protection, cross-platform analysis, and intellectual property rights issues²⁵. They are also actively searching for opportunities to communicate with academia regarding CTDS. Both industry and the academic community explore the value of IPD DS, which is yet to be fully realised. Both communities need high level evidence on the CTDS value

¹⁷ Taichman DB, et al. (2017): Data Sharing Statements for Clinical Trials: A Requirement of the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1002315.

¹⁸ Warren E (2016): Strengthening Research through Data Sharing. DOI: 10.1056/NEJMp1607282.

¹⁹ Ohmann C, et al. (2021): Status, use and impact of sharing individual participant data from clinical trials: a scoping review. DOI: 10.1136/bmjopen-2021-049228.

²⁰ Macleod MR, et al. (2014): Biomedical research: increasing value, reducing waste. DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(13)62329-6.

²¹ International Consortium of Investigators for Fairness in Trial DS, et al. (2016): Toward Fairness in Data Sharing. DOI: 10.1056/NEJMp1605654.

²² Naudet F, et al. (2021): Medical journal requirements for clinical trial DS: Ripe for improvement. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1003844.

²³ Mansmann U, et al (2023) Implementing clinical trial data sharing requires training a new generation of biomedical researchers, Nature Medicine (accepted, NMED-C120847B, https://cloud.ibe.med.uni-muenchen.de/umdtaiive2aiph3w/Paper_SHARE_CTD_final.pdf)

²⁴ Sudlow R, et al. (2016): EFSP/PSI working group on DS: accessing and working with pharmaceutical clinical trial patient level data-sets - a primer for academic researchers. DOI: 10.1186/s12874-016-0171-x.

²⁵ Schmidt H, et al. (2018): An Industry Experience with Data Sharing. DOI: 10.1056/NEJMc1805610.

within medical research will profit from established best practices in research using CTDS. Our activity is clearly reaching beyond the actual state-of-the-art. By developing, teaching and testing best practices and their impact, our outputs will influence the practices of the various academic and industrial stakeholders involved in the clinical trial landscape.

2.2 Soundness of the proposed methodology (including interdisciplinary approaches, consideration of the gender dimension and other diversity aspects if relevant for the research project, and the quality and appropriateness of open science practices)

Overall methodology: The objective of SHARE-CTD engages in meta- and methodological research to explore aspects of CTDS. SHARE-CTD is interdisciplinary and embraces: (1) *Clinical Trials Regulations*, (2) *Ethical, Legal, and Social Issues (ELSI)*, (3) *Medical Informatics*, (4) *Data Science*, (5) *Biostatistics*, (6) *Meta Research*, and (7) different medical fields (e.g. Neurology, Psychiatry, Oncology, Clinical Psychology). All partners, methods and disciplines are focused on developing and implementing Open Science practices.

Clinical Trials Regulations and frameworks for handling *ELSI* are a fast-developing field that includes both guidelines and international infrastructure. The respective competencies are provided from industrial and public partners (NFDI4Health, Bayer, ECRIN, NICE). Furthermore, concepts and guidelines are developing on how to implement *Open Science* into trial activities. Our partners METRICS and CFJ are leading the research on this field.

Medical Informatics studies theoretical and practical aspects of information processing and communication in medicine and health care. It works on open data models, open infrastructures, and technologies as well as concepts for Open Science and DS. There are high competencies within the core group of SHARE-CTD (Charité, UMG) as well as within our partners (NFDI4Health, ZB MED, YODA).

Data Science is especially focused on the organisation and analysis of complex data structures. Respective competencies are provided within the beneficiaries (Charité, LMU, UMCU, MUW, UMG, UZH) but also by our partners (SCr, SDAaS).

Biostatistics has developed a rich set of strategies for analysing clinical trial data. The development of statistical methods that can be executed in distributed settings and a closer cooperation with Medical Informatics and Data Sciences will make valuable contributions to developing new methods to protect patient privacy during data analysis. Both, beneficiaries (LMU, Charité, MUV, UMCU, UMG, UZH) and partners (Bayer, ZB MED) will provide respective competencies.

Meta Research applies the scientific method to study science itself, and is a powerful tool for identifying problems with scientific research and developing, implementing and evaluating targeted solutions. It also includes subjects like reporting science and journalology. Meta Research can be used to improve research efficiency and reliability, reduce waste and increase value²⁶. Experts on this field are at UR1, Charité, HCL, UPD and within the associated partners METRICS and CFJ.

²⁶ Ioannidis JPA, et al. (2015): Meta Research: Evaluation and Improvement of Research Methods and Practices. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pbio.1002264.

Integration of methods and disciplines to pursue the objectives: Work packages 3-5 define the interdisciplinary integration of methods and disciplines into the four objectives of SHARE-CTD .

WP3 comprises six ESR projects around *CTDS best practice* (Objective 1 and Objective 2, Figure 2). ESR5 (UMG, DMI) develops and evaluates methodology for innovative data re-usability and enriching existing data-sets with external knowledge (*FAIRification* and *Data Enrichment*, Meta-data). She/he will receive intensive guidance by a Medical Informatician and Data Scientist, but also input from medical terminology and clinical trial regulation (ECRIN). Shared use of data benefits from linking the study-specific records with additional data from different contexts from health care or billing, from extended context towards the interpretation of the data (NFDI4Health). The activities of ESR3 (Charité, BIH) on *anonymization* are supervised by a Medical Informatician with expertise in privacy protection techniques and supported by ELSI input and expertise in trial regulations (Bayer, ECRIN, YODA). Emphasis will be placed on how anonymisation can be combined with additional safeguards used in CTDS platforms (e.g. fine-grained, role-based access control) to maximise the usability of shared data while ensuring appropriate privacy protection for the data subjects. ESR1 (LMU, IBE) works on proper *Validation* and needs supervision by a biostatistician and input from sharing platform specialists (YODA). The work is based on a recent Cochrane Review which assessed the validity of 96 prognostic and predictive models for patients with multiple sclerosis²⁷. ESR1 develops and evaluates innovative methodology to perform large scale validation using data from CTDS platforms and provides solutions for missing methodology. Especially, the need to use several sharing platforms poses specific challenges and refers to work of ESR3. Her/his work may be also inspired by the work of ESR8 and ESR 9. ESR8 (UU, JC) studies *Cross-Design Synthesis* and explores how decision making and health technology assessment is affected by (changes in) the amount, type (e.g. non-randomised) and format (e.g. individual participant data instead of aggregate data) of available evidence. ESR8 will develop and evaluate statistical methodology to combine data from randomised and non-randomised studies as well as instruments to ascertain the transparency, openness and reproducibility of evidence generated from individual data sources (MUW, NICE). ESR9 (MUW, CeMSIIS) assesses and develops statistical methodology for the design and analysis of randomised clinical trials utilising external data, e.g., to augment control groups, focusing on methods that adjust for bias based on measured confounders, variability between control groups, outcome variables or a combination thereof. ESR9 also reviews current practice and reporting of the selection process of external data (specification of data sources, inclusion/exclusion criteria, ...) and to quantify the potential bias introduced if, e.g., external control groups and analysis methods are selected when (partial) information on the control group data is available at the time of planning. To achieve these objectives ESR9 will use analytical methods and simulation studies to develop and assess respective Bayesian (Meta-analytic Predictive Prior distribution) and frequentist methods. The potential biases introduced by the knowledge of historic data at the time of trial planning will be assessed in a simulation study as well as in a case study based on a large clinical trial data base. The work of ESR9 combines Biostatistics as well as Data Science. ESR10 (UZH, DB) will work on selective outcome reporting which occurs when only a subset of the originally recorded outcomes of a clinical trial is reported. For example, benefit outcomes that are non-significant and harm outcomes that are unfavourable to the treatment considered may be less likely to be reported. The availability of individual patient-level data will provide complete information on primary, secondary and harm thus enabling to assess the accuracy of meta-analytic adjustment methods in the presence of outcome reporting bias

²⁷ <https://www.cochranelibrary.com/cdsr/doi/10.1002/14651858.CD013606/full> [08.11.2022]

(ORB) through simulation. Furthermore, the extent of ORB in the medical literature will be assessed through a systematic comparison of the outcomes reported in available publications against the set of originally recorded outcomes. ESR10 needs input from Biostatistics as well as Medical Informatics and medical expertise (UR1, NFDI4Health).

WP4 comprises five ESR projects which study the impact of CTDS in the medical literature (Objective 3 and Objective 4, Figure 2). ESR7 (HCL, SREC) is working on the understanding and accepting DS within patients and needs input from Medical Ethics as well as from Data Science and Medical Informatics to explore technical as well as ethical aspects of the interaction between trials data sharing and its perception by patients. On the one hand this work defines different issues how concepts of CTDS are reflected by patients, on the other hand it defines best practice to inform about and engage trial participants in CTDS. ESR2 (UR1, IRSET) explores the *impact of CTDS* on medical research as reflected in the medical literature. ESR2 uses meta-analytic approaches and Meta Research strategies (CFJ, METRICS). The development of *automated screening tools* by ESR4 relies of Data Science and informatics tools for natural language processing (SCr). These results will feed in the Meta Research strategies as used by ESR2 and ESR11. ESR6 (UPD, DGP) assesses the added value of IPDMA in mental health and needs input from clinical psychology, psychotherapeutic research and Meta Research methods (large-scale umbrella review, meta-epidemiologic approach). ESR6 also performs a qualitative analysis using surveys and interviews with main authors of IPDMA to identify reasons for lack of participation, beyond what is reported in the paper. ESR11 (UR1, CIC) will assess the impact of clinical trial data sharing in terms of reproducibility of study results for pivotal trials shared by the study sponsor. This project will start with a pilot survey of all pivotal trials in oncology submitted to the European Medicine Agency and will reproduce their results on the main outcome(s) and all safety results. This project will develop a strategy for re-analyses and will help to pilot-test a label “reproducible science” for reproducible trials, a new incentive for sharing trial data and reproducing main results.

WP5 defines three network-based datathons (Figure 2). They teach values by promoting transparency, honesty and collaboration in an environment where ideas can be shared openly and implementation can become more efficient. The **first datathon** (D1) will introduce a single RCT data-set. Participants will apply and critically assess the FAIR principles in order to reproduce a specific analysis result. The ESRs will be split in five teams and each will re-analyse the same RCT following a standardised procedure. It is important to explore topics related to inferential reproducibility²⁸ of RCTs. In the **second datathon** (D2), each team of researchers will design and perform an IPD meta-analysis. Teams will review each other’s IPDMA protocols using standard checklists for conduct and reporting to assess quality and transparency. Participants will benefit from the input of experts within the project and external advisors (patients/clinicians). After conducting their IPD meta-analysis, ESRs will have the opportunity to contact the original investigators. All results will be compared at the end of the workshop to explore topics related to inferential reproducibility²⁹ and overlapping meta-analyses based on the same PICO³⁰. The **third datathon** (D3) focuses on a secondary analysis of clinical trial data, using data-sets from the second Datathon. Each team will define an interesting research question that requires data re-use and explore their question using the data-sets. D3 follows the example of the

²⁸ Goodman SN, et al. (2016): What does research reproducibility mean? DOI: 10.1126/scitranslmed.aaf5027.

²⁹ Naudet F, et al. (2018): Data sharing and reanalysis of randomized controlled trials in leading biomedical journals with a full DS policy: survey of studies published in *The BMJ* and *PLOS Medicine*. DOI: 10.1136/bmj.k400.

³⁰ Ioannidis JPA (2016): The Mass Production of Redundant, Misleading, and Conflicted Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses. DOI: 10.1111/1468-0009.12210.

SPRINT challenge³¹. There is a series of cross-project and network-wide scientific topics (Guidelines, output of datathons, comment papers, ...). The **Working Group Scientific Input** will coordinate and supervise these interdependent common activities.

Gender dimension and other diversity do not play a specific role in our research projects except in the project on *understanding and accepting DS within patients* where sex-specific design and analyses need to be implemented.

Open Science practices: SHARE-CTD aims to diffuse **sound and trustworthy science** and considers Open Science as a unique opportunity to reach this objective³². The working paradigm of SHARE-CTD reflects Open Science principles and uses related instruments and infrastructures: Published protocols, open access publications, making data available and sharable, using the Open Science Framework (OSF) and similar tools (EOSC and more). SHARE-CTD will also provide massive training in Open Science strategies. The commitment of the team towards Open Science will maximise the diffusion and impact of the SHARE-CTD programme. To ensure transparency and reproducibility for each project, study protocols will be drafted according to appropriate guidelines and pre-registered on the OSF. In addition, we plan to submit each study as a registered report³³, ideally on *Open Research Europe*³⁴. Reporting will follow current standards and data and codes will be shared, when it is legally and ethically feasible (e.g. for all Meta Research projects). In other words, SHARE-CTD will not solely assess best Open Science practices/evaluate the impact of Open Science practices but it will also implement Open Science practices at every step of the research programme. Beneficiaries of the project are heavily involved in the Open Science movement (e.g. UM is part of LMU Open Science Centre, FN is part of the French Reproducibility Network, LH is UZH Open Science delegate and part of the Swiss reproducibility network, MP and TD discuss Open Science approaches with regulatory bodies, FP has supported multiple medical research projects with sharing data openly) and some of the beneficiaries (IC and FN) have proposed that Open Science should be appraised when assessing researcher for promotion and tenure³⁵ and that Open Science should be part of regulatory process in the field of drug evaluation³⁶. Our partners (METRICS, CFJ and YODA) are leaders in the field of Open Science. We will also ensure a large dissemination of our teachings concerning Open Science, using the project website. Last, whatever the outcome is for the SHARE-CTD, we will publish this application after its assessment.

Research data management and management of other research outputs: We will put particular emphasis on implementing the FAIR data principles, comprehensive research data management methods and Open Science principles. As an important pillar, a Data Management Plan (DMP) will be prepared during the Grant Agreement process and published by the management office (MO@LMU). The DMP will care on the findability of SHARE-CTD data/research outputs: Types of persistent and unique identifiers (e.g. digital object identifiers) and trusted repositories that will be used. It will be continuously updated throughout the project to reflect essential information on the collection, storage, management, sharing and archiving of data in the different WPs and research projects. To foster collaboration and communication, we will set up a web-based working environment consisting of private workspaces as well as group-specific and project-internal areas,

³¹ Burns NS, Miller PW (2017): Learning What We Didn't Know - The SPRINT Data Analysis Challenge. DOI: 10.1056/NEJMp1705323.

³² Munafò MR, et al. (2017): A manifesto for reproducible science. DOI: 10.1038/s41562-016-0021.

³³ <https://www.cos.io/initiatives/registered-reports> [08.11.2022].

³⁴ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/> [08.11.2022].

³⁵ Moher D, et al. (2018): Assessing scientists for hiring, promotion, and tenure. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pbio.2004089.

³⁶ Naudet F, et al. (2021): An Open Science pathway for drug marketing authorization - Registered drug approval DOI: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1003726.

based on Atlassian Confluence³⁷. MO@LMU will also provide a cloud environment (Nextcloud³⁸) which provides workspaces for each SHARE-CTD member to store data and documents. There will be the opportunity to interact actively in the cloud on writing or analysing.

Study protocols will be pre-registered and analysis scripts will be made available as Open Code (Git repositories and DOI). Relevant project results will be published in peer-reviewed high-impact open access journals and on the European Commission's open access publishing platform *Open Research Europe* to further maximise outreach and ensure free access for the widest possible readership. This will enable knowledge transfer to the scientific community and enable the general public to access our latest research findings. In SHARE-CTD, software is part of the research process and output. Hence, software will also be covered by our data management activities to ensure that results are fully reproducible. For this purpose, we will use a common software version control system (git) with an appropriate web-based frontend, such as GitLab, which is an open-source web application for version management of software projects offering advanced features such as issue tracking, Continuous Integration and Continuous Delivery (CI/CD) and a container registry. We follow state of the art in software development (FAIR guiding principles for Research Software, FAIR4RS)³⁹. Software artefacts will be published as open-source wherever possible. The data-sets created within SHARE-CTD will be made available following the FAIR principles.

Ethical aspects: Most of the research of SHARE-CTD uses already existing data sets provided on CTDS platforms. Data use agreements will be the basis of the data use. Each project will apply for assessment by the local IRB. For each data-set used, patients consented for the secondary data use needs to be given. The detailed project plans will also be discussed internally with the patient representative involved in SHARE-CTD. Additionally, two projects will perform surveys and interviews with patients and stakeholders. All project activities will be carried out involving a constant ethics and regulatory monitoring process in order to ensure transparency, fairness, and respect for individuals' fundamental rights, in compliance with the current regulations (ECRIN, NFDI4Health, NFDI ELSA). Relevant ethical issues are content of the training programme. In order to guarantee that development, deployment, and evaluation of AI-based methods follow sound ethical principles, SHARE-CTD adapts the Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI)⁴⁰ in each phase of the project. The consortium will guarantee the following ALTAI principles: human agency and oversight; privacy and data governance; transparency; fairness, diversity and non-discrimination; societal and environmental well-being; accountability.

Artificial Intelligence: The ESR4 project will use machine learning to create tools to detect CONSORT⁴¹ guideline elements in publications. The researcher will be further supported through ScreenIT⁴², a group of scientists and tool developers from North America, Europe and Australia who have created a variety of tools to screen the literature for common problems. ScreenIT is run by the ESR4 supervisor, Dr. Tracey Weissgerber (TW). The student will have a secondment with SciScore, which is an active ScreenIT contributor. ScreenIT members meet 1-3 times per month. These meetings will allow the student to collaborate and solicit advice and code from other toolmakers.

³⁷ <https://www.atlassian.com/software/confluence> [08.11.2022].

³⁸ <https://nextcloud.com/> [14.11.2022]

³⁹ <https://github.com/force11/FAIR4RS> [08.11.2022].

⁴⁰ <https://altai.insight-centre.org/> [08.11.2022].

⁴¹ <https://www.consort-statement.org/> [08.11.2022]

⁴² Weissgerber T, et al. (2021): Automated screening of COVID-19 preprints: can we help authors to improve transparency and reproducibility? DOI: 10.1038/s41591-020-01203-7.

ScreenIT has already created open source tools for identifying papers with open data and open code, detecting flow charts reporting inclusions, exclusions and attrition as well as tools that address blinding and randomisation. ScreenIT is currently conducting a comparison study to see which tool, or combination of tools, performs best for particular criteria. ESR4 will use existing tools, or combinations of tools, when possible, and create new tools to address further CONSORT elements.

The tools use regular expressions and Named Entity Recognition. Convolutional neural networks are used for tasks involving figures. Specific tools analyse tables. The ScreenIT pipeline allows to access information from many different parts of a manuscript and is validated using manually curated data from open access publications. Training data includes papers from many fields, journals and countries to ensure that we are capturing diverse reporting styles. The existing pipelines allow to screen papers in pdf and xml formats. No automated screening tool is perfect and reports from tools should be interpreted by a knowledgeable reader. Performance will be calculated using sensitivity, specificity and F1 scores (harmonic mean of precision and recall), and will be clearly reported in any place that the tools are applied. Known limitations of tools (e.g. common situations where the tool makes mistakes) will be clearly specified.

2.3 Quality and credibility of the training programme (including transferable skills, inter/multidisciplinary, inter-sectoral and gender as well as other diversity aspects)

Figure 3 shows six levels of competencies, which the ESRs will have to climb until the end

of the project. Level VI addresses the full understanding of the challenges, leverages, and barriers to CTDS and of Open Science practices. Level V reflects the familiarity with the four pillars of CTDS (Figure 1): Principles (FAIR, meta-data, privacy protection), Governance (rules, social contract, incentives, public good, pragmatic regulations), Skills (data management, assessing data quality, data analysis), Operations (handling systems, managing data, knowing research data infrastructures). On level IV, an ESR is familiar with the practices of CTDS as sharer (e.g. how to prepare data to be shared, how to comply with respective

ELSI, how to make data available) or as user (e.g. how to apply for access to shared data, how to write a data management plan, how to handle data use and access procedures, how to make one's own analysis project open). On level III, the ESR sees Meta Research as a practice for constant reflection and improvement of a scientific activity (e.g. evaluating the impact of CTDS). On level II, the ESR possesses skills for collaborative and reproducible research. On level I the ESR understands advanced methodology in CTDS (IPD meta-analyses, enrichment of clinical trial data by external data, concepts of re-analyses and reproducibility, distributed computing). Detailed knowledge will be set into increasingly broader contexts.

The training programme uses meetings to inspire and to steer interaction between ESRs and professionals: Content specific activities in form of breakout events, barcamps, moderated brainstorming events, small group instructions where participants teach each other's and share experiences, discussions to learn fair criticism. Instructions will be recorded and available to all ESRs before the events. During the meetings, discussions on content will deepen its understanding.

Local training is provided around individual research projects or by secondments. It may be enriched by joint activities of subgroups of ESRs and their supervisors. The detailed structure of the research program is presented in chapter 3.

The network-based training programme consists of *propaedeutic*, *schooling*, *datathons* (also part of research), *professional training* and a *conference*. Its contents are formalised to 30 ECTS (Table 1).

	Main Training Events & Conferences	ECT S	Lead Institution / Place	Action Month
1	Kick-off propaedeutic training	2	LMU / Munich	10
2	School (S1)	4	UHZ / Zürich	13
3	Datathon (D1)	4	UMG / Göttingen	16
4	Professional Training (PT1)	1		16
5	School (S2)	4	UMCU / Lyon	22
6	Datathon (D2)	4	UMCU / Utrecht	25
7	Professional Training (PT2)	1		25
8	School (S3)	4	UR1 / Online	31
9	Datathon (D3)	4	UR1 / Paris	34
10	Professional Training (PT3)	1		34
11	Final conference	1	LMU + BIH/ Berlin	44

Table 1: Main Network-Wide Training Events, Conferences and Contribution of Beneficiaries

In month 10, ESRs will meet for a two-week introductory propaedeutic training of the relevant fields. This event also includes community building to shape the interaction between ESRs and their supervisors. Each of the three following years will offer three weeks of network-based training, split in ten days of *schooling*, three days of *datathons*, and two days for *professional competences*. The role of the non-academic sector in the training programme is to give input to the network-based training and cooperate in secondments by forming internship projects. A conference will be used to summarise our findings and to allow our ESRs to showcase their state-of-the-art research. Individual secondments with our partners will offer ESRs practical experiences in specific CTDS environments.

Overview and content structure of the doctoral training programme:

The *Propaedeutic Training* introduces the key principles to request and access patient level data: Concepts of trial protocols and the legal/regulatory aspects of CTDS. ESRs will learn the management of complex data-sets by using meta-data (FAIR principles). An introduction to reproducibility issues and biostatistical principles for clinical trials is provided as well as to reporting guidelines and how Meta Research is performed on clinical trials results. This event will introduce all beneficiaries and partners to the group of ESRs and put them on the same starting positions. It will be used to calibrate expectations on both sides and design individual career development plans (CDPs).

Schooling events: The topic of the **first school** (S1) is *Data management and analytical skills for sharer/re-users*. Teaching will extend basic knowledge on clinical trial design, trial protocols (and their submission to an ethics committee), standards for clinical trials data (e.g. CDISC, relationship to FAIR, OMOP for non-randomized studies) and analysis (developing a statistical analysis plan), good practice in statistical computing (reproducible workflows), standards of data protection in CTDS (demonstrated by an anonymisation game), legal frameworks for DS (entering a DS agreement, tailored sharing approaches,

e.g. federated network, or sharing of specific aggregate data following an SAP), techniques to prepare a data-set for DS, adopting an Open Science workflow. The **second school** (S2) is on *Best practices in DS and Meta Research*. Teaching will cover: Innovative strategies for data protection and their relevance for CTDS (methods of privacy preserving analyses and federated computing); overview of the different patient level data access models; IPD related topics as basic principles of meta-analysis, methods for combining IPD from multiple trials (and possibly non-randomised studies), methods for comparing multiple interventions, and methods for addressing data quality issues (missing data, measurement error, confounding); advanced use of Open Science workflows, and tools and their application in Meta Research. The ELSI training introduce the topics: CTDS from a legal, societal, and philosophical point of view as well as state of the art how to do research on patients' perception of CTDS. The **third school** (S3) is on the *Impact of CTDS* and covers the topics: Instruments to incentivise CTDS, instruments to measure the impact of CTDS, advanced issues in Meta Research on the impact of CTDS. How to measure the impact of data sharing from the perspective of different stakeholders? What are the challenges for the industry / academia to perform CTDS?

Datathons: Datathons need time to be prepared, to do active work on the data, to discuss the results within and between teams, and to write a manuscript. Parts 2 and 3 will be in presence. Each datathon will be started during the schooling event before. Teams will learn about the topic and implementation details. SHARE-CTD members will build 5 teams. During the three months after the schooling event, the ESRs and their supervisors (accompanied by volunteer clinicians from our medical centres) will develop and register a protocol (or project proposal). Protocols will be reviewed by different stakeholders (e.g. input from patients on relevant outcomes, input from statisticians on the analysis plan, input from clinicians on research question, etc.). ESRs will have to handle ethical, privacy protection, and intellectual property issues. They will have to formulate hypotheses based on a state-of-the-art literature search, develop an analytic plan, and decide how to present the results. They have to handle a complex data-set by using the FAIR principles. Each team will implement an appropriate Open Science pipeline to perform their analyses (E.g. registration of the statistical analysis plan, sharing of code etc.). Data will be provided by our partner YODA within a secure DS environment⁴³. Conduct of these projects and transparent reporting of the corresponding results will use guidelines such as PRISMA-IPD or TRIPOD-Cluster. The different teams will work according to the *Many Analyst Project*⁴⁴ format to explore whether there are converging or divergent views. *Many Analysts' projects* focus on the diversity of views for a data-analytic task and systematically assess whether results and conclusions are dependent on the chosen analytical strategy. These projects elucidate the need for formal reproducible workflows and specific scientific strategies to address divergent views. In the **first datathon** (D1), participants will re-analyse a clinical trial. As an output, the group will draft a collaborative research paper about inferential reproducibility of this specific clinical trial. In the **second datathon** (D2), each team of researchers will design and perform an IPD meta-analysis. As an output, the group will draft a collaborative research paper about inferential reproducibility of this specific IPD meta-analysis. The **third datathon** (D3) focuses on a secondary analysis of clinical trial data and follows the example of the SPRINT challenge⁴⁵: The importance of the work will be assessed by a jury of patients and the scientific quality of the work will be assessed by the members of the network. Patients, domain experts and clinicians will be involved both as external advisors to provide feedback, and as part of a jury that will assess the potential

⁴³ <https://yoda.yale.edu/policies-procedures-guide-external-investigator-access-clinical-trial-data> [08.11.2022].

⁴⁴ Aczel B, et al. (2021): Consensus-based guidance for conducting and reporting multi-analyst studies. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.72185.

⁴⁵ Burns NS, Miller PW (2017): Learning What We Didn't Know - The SPRINT Data Analysis Challenge. DOI: 10.1056/NEJMp1705323.

impact of each research question. As an output, the group will draft a collaborative research paper about secondary analyses of clinical trial data.

Professional training will be organised in three two-day sessions. The **first professional training** (PT1) will involve community building elements with focus on developing skills for: (1) How to interact into a multicultural setting, (2) team building, (3) success skills, (4) moderation skills, (5) presenting scientific research in social media. The **second professional training** (PT2) will concentrate on employment issues for our ESRs from the perspective of the different stakeholders involved in the project. It will also introduce negotiating issues and offer advice regarding communication between data holders and researchers. PT2 will address a variety of stakeholders, including the pharmaceutical industry, academia and regulatory authorities. The **third professional training** (PT3) will assess the scientific results of the ESRs from different viewpoints using the impact criteria discussed in the third schooling event, which focus on the values of the network (openness, DS and societal impact). This session will include a specific workshop organised by PhD students, focused on what ESRs have learned, where the group succeeded vs. failed in CTDS, and how the scientific community can do CTDS better.

Conference: We will close our project with a conference summarising and presenting our results and experiences to the different stakeholders and expecting their feedback.

Internships: Internships are crucial for ESRs to gain experience with different CTDS issues related to best practice and impact, the two underlying components of our programme structure. ESRs will gain insight into best practices by working with our industrial and academic partners who perform CTDS. Academic partners for internships are METRICS, CFJ, YODA,

Training interaction within the network: We will run Virtual Brainstorming Events⁴⁶ to collaboratively work on papers and discuss insights and lessons learned after each datathon or schooling event. Virtual Brainstorming Events consist of two-three days of virtual brainstorming, where participants explore pre-defined topics by sharing ideas, insights and experiences. The asynchronous discussions allow participants to contribute to the conversation when they have time, facilitate creativity, and allow ideas to evolve. Finally, events include a virtual open space, where participants can organise spontaneous in-depth conversations on topics of interest. All network participants will learn to organise and moderate Virtual Brainstorming Events, so that participants can use this format to prepare guidelines and recommendations or collaborate on shared projects across centres.

Role of non-academic sector in the training programme: Non-academic partners represent a wide spectrum of practical requirements needed to maximise ESRs employability on the job market. Their contributions to a training programme ensure that participants develop essential (practical) skills required by non-academic employers. Partners contribute relevant research questions on best practices in CTDS and declared to harmonise their activities to provide a harmonised setting for training, research, and secondments. Non-academic partners also contribute a large variety of practical/regulatoric experiences.

ECRIN-ERIC: The European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network is committed to promoting and enhancing the sharing of IPD from clinical trials for secondary analyses. It is involved in respective research and training projects and provides a rich infrastructure.

⁴⁶ Holman C, et al. (2021): How to connect academics around the globe by organizing an asynchronous virtual unconference. DOI: 10.12688/wellcomeopenres.16893.2.

ECRIN provides training and opportunities for secondments. **ECRIN will contribute to S1, S2, D1, PT2. ECRIN also provides secondments. Bayer AG** actively performs clinical trials and shares IPD via the platform CSDR. **It provides training (S1, PT2) and opportunities for secondments. SciCrunch** is devoted to improving descriptions of research methods, resources and reagents in scientific papers. It is part of the ScreenIT team. **SciCrunch will provide one opportunity for secondment and contribute to training (S3). Information Centre for Life Sciences (ZB MED)** is an infrastructure and research centre for information and data in the life sciences. Its goal is to support and strengthen research for the benefit of people and the environment: from medicine and biodiversity to environmental protection. It is part of the NFDI4Health consortium and **provides training (S1, D1-D3) and opportunities for secondments. NICE:** The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence provides national guidance and advice to improve health and social care in England. NICE's role is to improve outcomes for people using the NHS, public health and social care services by producing evidence-based guidance and advice for health, public health and social care practitioners; developing quality standards; and providing a range of information services for commissioners, practitioners and managers across health and social care. **NICE provides training (S2, PT2) and opportunities for secondments. Dife:** The German Institute of Human Nutrition Potsdam-Rehbruecke researches the influence of nutrition on health. The overall goal is to make scientific knowledge usable for prevention and therapy. In order to translate new approaches most efficiently from the lab to patients, the scientists at Dife work in a combination of experimental and applied research: from cells and mice to epidemiological observations and human intervention. **Dife shares data on a regular basis and provides training (S1, PT3) and opportunities for secondments. Smart Data Analysis and Statistics** supports pharmaceutical companies and contract research organizations in the analysis of clinical trials and real-world data. **They will provide input to the training programme (S2, D2) and offer a secondment.**

2.4 Quality of the supervision (including mandatory joint supervision for industrial and joint doctorate projects)

Qualifications and supervision experience of supervisors: All eleven supervisors have qualifications with respect to guiding, supporting, directing, advising, and mentoring.

Supervisor (Institution) and Description
<p>Ulrich Mansmann (LMU, coordinator) is a trained biostatistician and clinical epidemiologist. He is Full Professor and Chair of Biometrics and Bioinformatics at the University of Munich (LMU) and chairs the master programme MSc Epidemiology as well as the PhD programme Public Health and Epidemiology at the LMU medical faculty. UM is also spokesman of the national working group DS of the German Medical Informatics Initiative (MII). During his career, he was supervising more than 40 master and 20 PhD students. He was responsible biometrician in more than 30 Phase III IIT RCTs and has successfully concluded many research projects (over 380 listed PubMed publications). He is also member of the LMU's IRB as well as the Data Use and Access Committee (DUAC).</p>
<p>Florian Naudet (UR1) is a psychiatrist, Meta Researcher and former post-doctoral fellow at METRICS. He is Full Professor and Chair of Therapeutics at Rennes University. He has a strong interest in studying research wastes and DS practices. He has worked in the fields of clinical pharmacology, research methodology, epidemiology, and neurosciences contributing more than 100 PubMed-listed publications. He supervised 15 MD and two PharmD theses as well as four PhD and five master students. He leads a French research programme on reproducibility of therapeutic research and co-leads the "DS statement" working group for the French Ministry of Research.</p>
<p>Clara Locher (UR1) is a PharmD with a PhD in oncology pharmacology and therapeutics. She is currently assistant professor in pharmacology and methodology. Her research interests are quality, transparency and reproducibility of trials studying targeted therapy in oncology. She has also a big interest in Meta Research and explores areas related to scientific integrity. She is an early career researcher and supervised one MD thesis as well as five master students and one PhD. She is member of the research programme on reproducibility of</p>

Supervisor (Institution) and Description
therapeutic research led by UR1.
Fabian Prasser (Charité, BIH) is a Full Professor of Medical Informatics at the Berlin Institute of Health (BIH) at Charité. He currently supervises more than ten PhD students with doctoral topics in the field of DS and data protection and offers corresponding methodological and practical courses as part of the PhD programme Health Data Sciences at the Charité. He is co-leader of corresponding work packages in several national and international research projects (DFG, BMBF, H2020) and coordinates the module Medical Informatics of the Master's programme in Epidemiology at the Berlin School of Public Health. He is also PI of Charité's subproject in the Medical Informatics Initiative (MI-I).
Tracey Weissgerber (Charité, BIH) is a Group Leader at the BIH QUEST Center for Responsible Research. Her research focuses on improving the quality of reporting, data visualisation and statistical analysis in the scientific literature. Her work has contributed to policy changes in many journals. She has supervised students in a variety of contexts (more than 50 undergraduate and graduate students completing hands-on laboratory internships, supervising a Masters student, and contributing to mentorship and supervision of seven clinician-scientists and research trainees). She leads the Wellcome Trust Funded SPOKES programme, which provides group mentorship and support to five mid-career fellows, five junior fellows and a think tank of twelve early career researchers working on science improvement projects.
Ulrich Sax (UMG) is professor in Medical Informatics and the head of the Translational Research Informatics (TRI) research group within the Department of Medical Informatics of UMG. He provides a long-term experience in design, operation and validation of information infrastructure for health care and translational research. He was involved in the design of several interdisciplinary curricula including the (international) Göttingen Medical Informatics and Data Science curricula. He graduated 34 Master students and seven PhDs, currently supervises three PhD candidates and two Postdocs. His research focusses on the integration and visualisation of heterogeneous phenotype and genotype data in healthcare and biomedical informatics research.
Evelyne Decullier (HCL) is a methodologist in the public health department of Hospices Civils de Lyon. Her scientific interests are in publication bias, retractions, reporting of affiliations, and development of paramedical research. She is also involved in research ethics committees and works actively in a network to develop integrity. Furthermore, her interest lies the patient's attitudes towards CTDS. She also accompanied eight master students and one PharmD thesis and got recently appointed at the French council for scientific integrity.
Martin Posch (MUW) is professor of Medical Statistics and head of the Institute for Medical Statistics (IMS) and Center for Medical Statistics, Informatics and Intelligent Systems (CeMSIIS) at the Medical University of Vienna. MP's main research interests are group sequential trials, adaptive designs and multiple testing, focusing on applications in clinical trials and Bioinformatics. M. Posch has supervised four postdoctoral researchers, and graduated three PhD. MP (co-)led several work packages in EU funded projects, as the EU patient-centric clinical trial platform (EU-PEARL). MP is associate editor of Biometrics and Biometrical Journal and advisory board member of Statistics in Biopharmaceutical Research and the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety. MP worked as statistical expert at the European Medicines Agency (EMA) from 2011 to 2012, where he contributed to guideline development and the assessment of study designs. He serves as Observer of the EMA Biostatistics Working Party and member of its Platform Trials Task Force, and member of the Advisory board of the Austrian Regulatory Agency.
Ioana Alina Cristea (UPD) is Associate Professor of Clinical Psychology, as well as a Meta Researcher, with a focus on meta-analyses. She is faculty member for the PhD programme UPD. She has supervised over 20 Master theses, is a co-supervisor of three PhD students and post-doctoral advisor of one student.
Valentijn de Jong (UMCU, JC) is an assistant professor at the Julius Center for Health Sciences and Primary care, University Medical Center Utrecht, and is seconded to the Data Analytics and Methods Task Force of the European Medicines Agency. His work is focused on methods for clustered data such as individual participant data meta-analyses. He has developed and evaluated statistical methodology and has produced multiple open source R packages. He coordinates courses on individual participant data meta-analysis, and has lectured various other biostatistical and epidemiological courses. He has supervised five MSc students, and currently supervises one PhD candidate.
Leonhard Held (UZH) is Full Professor and Chair of Biostatistics at the University of Zurich (UZH). He is Programme Director of the UZH Master Programme in Biostatistics, Open Science Delegate and Director of the Centre for Reproducible Science at UZH, and member of the steering committee of the Swiss Reproducibility Network (www.swissrn.org). He has supervised 50+ Master and 20+ PhD theses in his career.

Quality of the joint supervision arrangements and progress monitoring: Each ESR will follow the rules defined by her/his local PhD programme. Additionally, we will establish for each ESR a Thesis Advisory Committee (TAC) composed as required by the hosting institution and with at least one additional supervisor from the Consortium. This way, each TAC consists of at least two members of SHARE-CTD. In the first six months each ESR will develop a research plan specifying milestones and deliverables as publications and conference participation. The TAC will be responsible for supporting ESRs in developing the RP, implementing the research projects, updating a Personal Career Development Plan, and providing supervision, coaching and guidance. Every six months a joint meeting of the TAC with the ESR will be held to evaluate the ESRs progress and to update the research plan if necessary. This way potential problems can be identified and resolved in a timely manner. The supervisor(s) at the host institution will meet fortnightly with the ESR and provide supervision, technical assistance and feedback. Additionally, ESRs will choose a mentor either from the host institution or from the Consortium, who will support and advocate for the ESR if problems with the TAC occur. All mentors will have substantial relevant expertise or a strong background in supporting career development. There will be a half-yearly exchange between all TACs regarding the experiences related to the supervision activities. In case of conflicts between the ESRs and their supervisors, the ESRs can contact the Ombudsman. It is of interest that frictions get harmonized as early as possible.

3 IMPACT

Open Science is an emerging paradigm for scientific practice to increase societal value and reduce waste of resources⁴⁷. It is a policy priority for the European Commission⁴⁸. The G7 clearly calls for open practices in science as one of their top priorities⁴⁹. As part of Open Science, data sharing (DS) is a central concept to reach transparency, openness, and reproducibility⁵⁰. Besides its scientific aspects, DS allows new forms of evidence synthesis with high economic value⁵¹ and inspires further innovation. DS is the basis for an effective use of a common good. In August 2022, the White House Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) released new policy guidance to ensure more equitable access to federally funded research⁵².

Data from clinical trials are of high public interest and its transparency is requested as announced in a meeting in 2012 between the European Medicines Agency (EMA) and pharmaceutical companies⁵³. Also, the US-American Federal Drug Agency (FDA) launched initiatives on clinical trial data transparency. The pharmaceutical industry reacted by proposals on how to share clinical trial data at the patient level (individual patient data, IPD). Medical journals stated to insist on more transparency before publishing papers. Also, the medical academic community is on the move. However, except for certain specific areas such as genetic epidemiology, DS is currently not well established⁵⁴.

Facing these very broad societal and scientific developments, our project aims to have an impact in three areas: Enabling scientists to practice CTDS, providing insights into the practice of CTDS, anchoring basic tenets of CTDS in scientific practice and public. The

⁴⁷ Nosek BA, et al. (2015): SCIENTIFIC STANDARDS. Promoting an open research culture. DOI: 10.1126/science.aab2374.

⁴⁸ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en [09.11.2022].

⁴⁹ <http://www.g8.utoronto.ca/science/2016-tsukuba-en.pdf> [09.11.2022].

⁵⁰ Popkin G (2019): Data sharing and how it can benefit your scientific career. DOI: 10.1038/d41586-019-01506-x.

⁵¹ Mijuk G (2020): The data42 program shows Novartis' intent to go big on data and digital. <https://www.novartis.com/stories/data42-program-shows-novartis-intent-go-big-data-and-digital> [09.11.2022].

⁵² Marcum CS, Donohue R (2022): Breakthroughs for All: Delivering Equitable Access to America's Research.

<https://www.whitehouse.gov/ostp/news-updates/2022/08/25/breakthroughs-for-all-delivering-equitable-access-to-americas-research/> [09.11.2022].

⁵³ Koenig F, et al (2015): Sharing clinical trial data on patient level: Opportunities and challenges. DOI: 10.1002/bimj.201200283.

⁵⁴ Stuart D, et al. (2018): Whitepaper: Practical challenges for researchers in data sharing. DOI: 10.6084/m9.figshare.5975011.v1.

intended impact is on a personal level (education of well-trained expert on CTDS who will make an impact on the practice of CTDS during their future career), on the level of scientific community (providing evidence for the impact of CTDS, creating increased attention for the practice and value of CTDS, providing guidance), and on a societal level (CTDS makes clinical trials data to a common good and strengthens scientific credibility within the society, it implements important ethical principles in clinical research).

3.1 Contribution to structuring doctoral training at the European level and to strengthening European innovation capacity, including the potential for:

Meaningful contribution of the non-academic sector to the doctoral training: As described in chapter 1, SHARE-CTD is built on a strong cooperation between the academic and non-academic sector. As mentioned above, the pharmaceutical industry is prepared to provide clinical trial data for reuse and research. They have already developed concepts and processes to support CTDS, whereas the academic sector is more reluctant to cooperate in CTDS as a joint undertaking. Therefore, the non-academic sector will stimulate ideas and can provide solutions for challenges in CTDS. The non-academic sector is also highly interested in winning CTDS experts who know how to handle this complex task. It is also interested in sharing new methodological progress regarding IPD analyses with the academic experts. Regulators and health agencies also show high interest in CTDS. In detail, the non-academic sector will make valuable contributions regarding regulatory issues, data management (standardisation and data quality management), and trial logistics. The non-academic sector recognizes that CTDS enables innovation. Companies like Roche, Novartis, Pfizer are building large datacentres to enable internal CTDS or CTDS between peers. Therefore, our programme will strengthen the innovation capacity within pharmaceutical companies, joint ventures between academic and non-academic sectors, or academic research based on high quality data provided by pharma. Guided by our non-academic partners, SHARE-CTD also tries to stimulate the implementation of concepts and principles of CTDS into the academic sector. Finally, research and teaching activities within SHARE-CTD fit in the concept of the European Health data space⁵⁵ that supports the use of health data for better healthcare delivery, better research, innovation and policy making and enables the EU to make full use of the potential offered by a safe and secure exchange, use and reuse of health data.

As stated before CTDS is at the basis of medical translation and innovation in personalised medicines. There is a clear interdisciplinary development in strengthening AI application on large databases in all scientific fields. But this broad vision needs a carefully developed infrastructure to allow applications that respect personal as well as IP rights, are easy to implement and use a sound methodology for evidence synthesis or creation. They also built on high quality *standardized* data-sets accompanied with the respective meta-data. Research and teaching within SHARE-CTD will contribute relevant input to make this vision real for clinical trials data.

Developing sustainable elements of doctoral programmes after the end of the DN funding: Using a participatory approach, and involving representatives of leading universities and organisations across Europe, the exploitation strategy has the goal of promoting and triggering a sustainable uptake of the SHARE-CTD concepts and materials in the curriculum of existing (medical or Data Science and Open Science oriented) PhD and Master programmes around Europe (UR1: MSc Public Health will directly benefit from the SHARE-CTD training materials; LMU: MSc Epidemiology, MSc Public Health; UZH ;

⁵⁵ https://health.ec.europa.eu/publications/proposal-regulation-european-health-data-space_en [09.11.2022].

MSc Biostatistics). Our cooperation with the CFJ is an opportunity to exchange innovative ideas about CTDS between Canada and Europe with respect to data-champion programmes⁵⁶. To ensure a large dissemination of the training material, SHARE-CTD received the support of the European Association of Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics (EACPT). We will use this connection to disseminate training material for EACPT members (e.g. during the congresses and/or dedicated workshops). A similar task is taken by LORIER that is an academic French stakeholder with strong imbedding in European research structures. All teaching material developed by SHARE-CTD will be available online (website, YouTube channel, ...).

3.2 Credibility of the measures to enhance the career perspectives and employability of researchers and contribution to their skills development

SHARE-CTD maximises the employability of the scientists (statisticians, data-managers, trialists, MDs, computer scientists) by seizing new hiring opportunities in the field of clinical trials (academia, industry, regulatory agencies, journals, research funding agencies, ...). The programme boosts research by using innovative IT, data management, regulatory knowledge, and cooperation structures. The composition of our consortium will open a broad range of career perspectives for our ESRs:

1. More and more institutions are motivated to provide technical and administrative CTDS services. These providers (e.g. YODA, Vivli, CSDR, and any other particular platforms) rely on well trained staff who knows to work with terminologies and meta-data, providing suitable anonymisation, complying with legal as well as data protection rules. Comparable technical and organisational infrastructure will develop in Europe that needs to be run and continuously improved by staff knowing the challenges of CTDS for data curation (data curators, data stewardship, data engineers, software developers, software architects). This applies to both the private and public sector.
2. Each CTDS platform needs a complex and thorough, but also efficient review process of the data sharing applications. Experts performing these reviews need to understand their interdisciplinary character. Even being expert in a specific field (medicine, biostatistics, Data Science, intellectual property, privacy protection, ELSI) they need an overarching understanding of this process.
3. The peer review of research papers created by CTDS requests an interdisciplinary approach and interdisciplinary competencies. Respective scientists need a clear understanding of its complexity and value. Editors or editorial staff require respective competencies to boost CTDS within their journals' activities.
4. Preparing CTDS is a highly demanded activity. Pharmaceutical industry implemented guidelines⁵⁷ and run specific departments to perform this task. Academic institutions (like trial centres at academic hospitals) follow and need well trained staff to set-up and contribute to CTDS activities. This may also be relevant for data-managers and data-engineers who necessitate skills on creating data-sets for sharing.
5. Research funders look for staff familiar with the complex issue of CTDS. More general, research management in academia, industry, governments, and regulators will need CDTS-knowledgeable personnel.
6. Building one's own research on shared data-sets will be a growing activity. Knowledge on how to structure this research will be crucial for a growing number of researchers. Future medical researcher will request a basic training on CTDS. This may also hold for data scientists active in the medical field. Our programme may provide the blueprint for the requested training (conceptual issues as well as online training materials).

⁵⁶ <https://alliancecan.ca/en/latest/news/announcing-2022-2023-data-champions> [09.11.2022].

⁵⁷ Eskola S (2017): EFPIA-PhRMA Principles successfully enable responsible clinical trial data sharing. <https://www.efpia.eu/news-events/the-efpia-view/blog-articles/29112017-efpia-phrma-principles-successfully-enable-responsible-clinical-trial-DS/> [09.11.2022].

7. Every activity improves through critical observation. CTDS needs Meta Research to be guided in acceptable directions and to be implemented in a fair and efficient way. Respective Meta Research may be driven by academic, professional institutions, but also by funders that are interested in improving their policies.

The philosophy of the SHARE-CTD programme is to maximise academic impact of research following the prism of the five “Hong Kong principles for assessing researchers”^{58,59}. They concern research and teaching activities that will put the emphasis on Open Science, reproducibility, responsible research practices, Meta Research. All outputs of SHARE-CTD along these five axes will ensure ESRs a high recognition in the Open Science community and beyond.

3.3 Suitability and quality of the measures to maximise expected outcomes and impacts, as set out in the dissemination and exploitation plan, including communication activities

SHARE-CTD will develop an integrated plan to disseminate its scientific, methodological, and policy achievements with focus on academic stakeholders, researchers, policy makers, health professionals, advocacy groups, and NGOs. The beneficiaries fully engage the partner organisations and ESRs in developing dissemination skills and engaging in dissemination activities. Two additional working groups will prepare a detailed dissemination plan and exploitation strategy, and will oversee the resulting activities (WG *dissemination and exploitation*, WG DE, with focus on professional stakeholders; WG *public engagement*, WG PE, with focus on the general public and scientific community). A logo will facilitate the recognition of SHARE-CTD contributions by stakeholders. In addition, all documents produced will be identified by project number and acronym.

General communication strategy for the research projects and Datathons: The deliverables of all research WPs contain integrated summaries of the evidence generated from both the individual ESR projects and the datathons. WG SI takes care on the provision of these deliverables, which will be disseminated widely to the scientific community by the WG DE and WG PE, which supports all research projects to publish their highly innovative ideas through journals and conference presentations as well as non-academic or public engagement venues and social media.

For research articles, the target publishing platform will be Open Research Europe. To ensure impact through reproducible research practices, each study protocol will be drafted according to appropriate guidelines and pre-registered on the OSF (and/or any equivalent registry, e.g. PROSPERO for IPD meta-analyses). In addition, when possible, we plan to submit research papers as registered reports (<https://cos.io/rr/>). SHARE-CTD members will use pre-prints servers to ensure rapid dissemination of findings. Reporting of research studies will follow current standards. All data and code will be shared on the OSF (or comparable platforms) when ethically and legally feasible.

Plan for the dissemination and exploitation activities, including communication activities: The SHARE-CTD Consortium will design the dissemination, exploitation and public engagement strategies based on the report published by the EC DG Research “Guide to successful Communications”⁶⁰ and has fully incorporated its principles. WG DE and WG PE will oversee all communication activities. ESRs will be trained in a variety of communication and dissemination skills, will be involved in both WGs and supported by the

⁵⁸ Moher D, et al. (2018): Assessing scientists for hiring, promotion, and tenure. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pbio.2004089.

⁵⁹ Moher D, et al. (2020): The Hong Kong Principles for assessing researchers: Fostering research integrity. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pbio.3000737.

⁶⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/h2020-guide-comm_en.pdf [9.11.2022]

LMU based Munich Science Communication Lab (MSCL)⁶¹. SHARE-CTD communication activities are presented in the Table 2-1 below.

Target audience	Strategy	Goals
All stakeholders: professional / general / public	Project webpage	To describe objectives, research projects and training activities, and make available news, public deliverables, articles, newsletters, and training materials; to provide interested stakeholders with accessible dissemination and communication material (brochures, leaflets, infographics). LMU will oversee the Webpage. It contains: Research programme / Consortium (PIs, ESRs and partners), / Research agenda (research projects, Datathons) / Training activities including training material / News and newsletters / Public deliverables / Research articles / Accessible dissemination and communication material (e.g. infographics about best practices, e.g. leaflet about how to increase impact of CTDS).
All stakeholders: general / public	Blog and social media	To inform the audience of SHARE-CTDs' results by means of an accessible health evidence blog and social media presence, both of which created by UR1. ESRs will contribute by translating highlights of their scientific papers into lay language. To create Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter accounts in SHARE-CTDs' name to inform, raise awareness of the project and foster exchanges with the target audience. A Meta Research blog and social media (LinkedIn and Twitter) will inform the audience of SHARE-CTD' results and news. PIs and ESRs will contribute by translating highlights of their scientific papers into lay language. We will also establish a SHARE-CTD YouTube channel.
Researchers and health professionals	Audio podcast, webinar series, presenting on conferences, providing short courses	To create ongoing information channels by developing an audio podcast and webinar series, including training webinars produced by partner organisations. Each ESR will be requested once a year to produce, with assistance from UR1 and LMU, a podcast and two webinars about their research projects. Besides specific Podcast platforms, contributions will also be available in our YouTube channel.
Researchers: academia / industry and students	Online training	Video clips of training events will be recorded, uploaded to the SHARE-CTD website and made available to academics and students. LMU will be responsible to provide resources. Contributions will also be available in our YouTube channel.
General public	Open doors days, CTDS challenge and similar activities	To make generated evidence accessible and raise awareness about CTDS, focusing on activities such as public science weeks of the hosting institution, where lectures and researchers are invited to present their work using lay language. ESRs will be supported to create and disseminate a "CTDS challenge" to promote awareness. To make Meta Research accessible and raise awareness about implication of SHARE-CTD, Open-Door Days will be organised during the Peer Review week with lectures and conferences using lay language. The peer review week is an annual scholarly communication event (in September) celebrating the value of peer review. The consortium will support this important event and thinks that it will the best moment to inform the public about the core values of DS.

Table 2: Dissemination aspects and WG DE / WG PE activities

Strategy for the management of intellectual property (IP), foreseen protection measures: We do not anticipate the need to invoke IP rights in any of the scientific deliverables of SHARE-CTD, as these documents will either be published Open Access and/or will be fully available to the public without charge on a pre-print server and/or on the

⁶¹ <https://www.mscl.de/> [9.11.2022]

SHARE-CTD website. General rules and specific measures will be covered in the consortium agreement. All material will be published under a CC BY-NC-ND or if reasonable a CC BY license.

General communication strategy for results with specific policy implications: SHARE-CTD has the ambition to influence scientific policies for clinical trials worldwide and at the European level by providing indisputable evidence on the value of clinical trial DS best practices. With the support of the SHARE-CTD consortium, ESRs will have to ensure that her/his research is taken up at the policy level by influencing the most important CTDS policies.

Members of the network have established connections with important policy makers: IC is a co-author of the Scoping report “reproducibility of scientific results in the EU” published by the European commission⁶². FN has been involved in the G7 working group about “research on research and open Science”. UM is influencing German Data Sharing policies as head of the respective national working group in the Medical Informatics Initiative. LH is member of the Open Science Ambassador ad-hoc group of the League of European Research Universities (LERU). Such contacts will help to disseminate our findings at a policy level. In WP6, SHARE-CTD will organise activities to translate our research (best practices/impact) into policy proposals.

SHARE-CTD will be committed to publish further concept papers and policy forums to disseminate its main results in important medical and/or scientific journals. All major generalist medical journals (such as NEJM, The Lancet, JAMA, the BMJ, Annals of internal medicine, and PLOS Medicine) have expressed their interest in DS policies. In addition, Science, Nature, eLIFE, and PLOS Biology have a major interest in the field of Meta Research and Data Sharing. The project will also disseminate its findings to the relevant scientific societies (e.g. European Association for Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics, International Society of Clinical Biostatistics, Society of Clinical Trials, International Society for Pharmacoepidemiology) and national funders (e.g. ANR, DFG, SNF).

The consortium’s communication strategy will rely on a website and on the broad use of social media to maximise visibility of its broad scientific value, its innovative research approach and methodologies. Especially, a YouTube channel will present the material (teaching, talks on results and activities), specific blogs and accounts by LinkedIn or Facebook will present our contents in different way (experts oriented, focusing the public). A key feature of SHARE-CTD training is to enable each ESR as an effective ambassador (e.g. on the website and in social media) and implementer (e.g. reproducible research practices) of her/his research; e.g. ESRs and PIs will be able to post on the blog to cover various facets of the programme. Blog posts are supposed to be engaged, focused on the core values of the SHARE-CTD project but may also cover other related topics. This will also be a strong contribution to science communication. Concrete plans for sections 2.3 must be included in the corresponding Table 3.1 b *Description of Work Packages*.

3.4 The magnitude and importance of the project’s contribution to the expected scientific, societal and economic impacts (project’s pathways towards impact)

⁶² Baker L, et al. (2020): Reproducibility of scientific results in the EU. DOI: 10.2777/341654.

Expected scientific impact(s): Despite a major interest in DS activities, we showed in our scoping review⁶³ that the exact impact of CTDS is still unknown. SHARE-CTD will address this gap by implementing an unprecedented comprehensive research programme, by identifying best practices and exploring how much clinical trial DS moves medical research forward faster (benefits and caveats).

SHARE-CTD will explore how far CTDS is effective. This information is currently lacking and will be crucial to inform policy makers, scientists and all stakeholders involved in clinical trials on the expected effects of DS. This very practical additional information will complement the ongoing implementation of DS policies under the current rules of academic publishing. SHARE-CTD will provide missing information about the usefulness and feasibility of large-scale DS policies and will produce good-practice guidelines for DS. The outputs will be particularly robust, original and liable to shape new DS policies and to establish a new norm in the clinical trial landscape. SHARE-CTD will provide a role model for evidence created by CTDS.

Expected economic/technological impact(s): We do not anticipate bringing new products, services, and business processes to the market. SHARE-CTD will provide results which also inform on economic aspects of CTDS. They may contribute to increase efficiency and to decrease costs as well as to modify standard settings of clinical trials. In addition, our commitment to Open Science will bring open tools (e.g. monitoring and rewarding DS) that may contribute to new scientific standards.

Expected societal impact(s): SHARE-CTD results will be informative in guiding future DS policies. For instance, in 2018, the BMJ editors wrote that they were considering changing their DS policy, drawing on the lessons of a previous observational study about their journal policy by some members of this consortium⁶⁴. This gives an idea of the impact of SHARE-CTD as a broader research programme including a large range of DS practices. SHARE-CTD has the potential to durably change medical journal policies worldwide and to shape a new landscape for clinical trial publishing by informing the ICMJE policies (with a possible impact on biomedical literature as a whole). SHARE-CTD may also inform commercial and non-commercial funders DS policies, worldwide as there is a critical need for harmonisation in this area⁶⁵.

SHARE-CTD has the potential to provide high grade convincing evidence on the value of CTDS for all stakeholders involved in therapeutic research (researchers, editors, funders, policy-makers and patients).

SHARE-CTD is not solely about answering a scientific question. It is about an ethical imperative: the responsibility towards study participants is the key idea beyond any ethical obligation to share clinical trial data⁶⁶. Patients put themselves at risk (to various degrees depending on the intervention studied) with uncertain individual benefits. This results in an implicit social contract imposing an ethical obligation that results should lead to the greatest possible benefit to society. The SHARE-CTD programme will address this ethical obligation by establishing the exact output of DS practices. Ultimately, our ethical obligation to clinical trial participants is to optimally use the data gathered to achieve improved clinical outcomes

⁶³ Ohmann C, et al. (2021): Status, use and impact of sharing individual participant data from clinical trials: a scoping review. DOI: 10.1136/bmjopen-2021-049228.

⁶⁴ Naudet F, et al. (2018): Data sharing and reanalysis of randomized controlled trials in leading biomedical journals with a full data sharing policy: survey of studies published in The BMJ and PLOS Medicine. DOI: 10.1136/bmj.k400.

⁶⁵ Gaba JF, et al. (2020): Funders' data-sharing policies in therapeutic research: A survey of commercial and non-commercial funders. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0237464.

⁶⁶ Taichman DB, et al. (2017): Data Sharing Statements for Clinical Trials: A Requirement of the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1002315.

and thereby benefit human health. SHARE-CTD will inform and define the best practices to achieve this goal.

The research agenda of SHARE-CTD and the evidence provided by it will influence teaching, practices, and scientific policies on clinical trials worldwide.

4 QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY OF THE IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 Quality and effectiveness of the work plan, assessment of risks and appropriateness of the effort assigned to work packages

SHARE-CTD is structured into seven WPs. WP1 is devoted to management and WP2 to training. WP3 to WP5 focus on research and define the tasks and deliverables of each ESR individual projects. WP6 handles policy implementation (scientific and regulatory aspects), WP7 organises broad and far-reaching activities on dissemination, communication (general audience and the public) and exploitation of the project’s results and deliverables. How they relate to each other is sketched in Figure 4.

WP No.	WP Title	Lead Beneficiary No.	Lead Beneficiary Short Name	Start Month	End month	Activity Type	Researcher involvement
1	Management	LMU	UM	1	48	Management	None
2	Training	UMCU	VJ	10	48	Training	All
3	Best Practice in CTDS	MUW, HCL	MP, ED	13	48	Research	ESR: 1, 3, 5, 8, 9, 10
4	Impact of CTDS on medical science	Charité/BHI	FP, TW	13	48	Research	ESR: 2, 4, 6, 7, 11
5	Datathons	UMG	US	13	48	Training Research	All
6	Knowledge translation and implementation	UR1	FN	13	48	Dissemination	All
7	Dissemination, communication and exploitation	LMU	UM	1	48	Dissemination	All

Recruitment Table per beneficiary

Researcher No.	Recruiting Participant (short name)	PhD awarding entities	Planned Start (months)	Duration (months)
ESR 1	UM	LMU	10	36
ESR 2	FN	UR1	10	36
ESR 3	FP	Charité	10	36
ESR 4	TW	Charité	10	36
ESR 5	US	UGOE	10	36
ESR 6	IAC	UPD	10	36
ESR 7	ED	UCBL	10	36
ESR 8	VJ	UU	10	36
ESR 9	MP	MUW	10	36
ESR 10	LH	UZH	10	36
ESR 11	CL	UR1	10	36
Total:11				

Research Projects, including secondment plan

Table 3.1 f: Individual Research Projects

Fellow	Host institution	PhD enrolment*	Start date	Duration	Deliverables
ESR 1	LMU	LMU	Month 10	36 months	D.ESR.1.1-4
Role of CTDS for validation of prognostic and predictive models for MS patients - WP 3, 5, 6					
Objectives: Use of data from large Phase III or Phase IV trials (available at CSDR, VIVLI, YODA) as well as large cohort data from a French MS research group (OFSEP). The ESR will explore methodological aspects how to validate prognostic/predictive models over different CTDS platforms and will work on solutions for missing methodology. It is of interest to learn from this activity more general aspects on validation challenges which could be communicated to other fields of clinical medicine and play an important role on best practice implementations.					
Expected Results: Protocol for the project (D.ESR.1.1), SAP (D.ESR.1.2), validation report for several models over several platforms (D.ESR.1.3), two research papers (D.ESR.1.4)					
Planned secondment(s): (1) Bayer (CG), months 18 – 20, to learn about the process of CTDS in a pharmaceutical company; (2) ECRIN (CK), months 27-29, to learn about the process of CTDS in an academic setting. (3) YODA (JR), months 36-38, to learn about the process of CTDS from a respective sharing platform					
Enrolment in Doctoral degree(s): LMU, Medical Faculty, PhD program Epidemiology and Public Health.					

Fellow	Host institution	PhD enrolment*	Start date	Duration	Deliverables
ESR 2	UR1		Month 10	36 months	D.ESR.2.1-4
Impact of clinical trial data sharing – WP 4, 5, 6					
Objectives: To assess the impact of clinical trial data sharing (in terms of re-use, published re-uses, impact of those re-uses and costs saved), we will triangulate evidence from different studies including: i) a large-scale observational study of current data-sharing policies in leading biomedical journals, ii) survey of data sharing practices in the biomedical literature and iii) methodological/simulation studies exploring potential pitfalls associated with data re-use.					
Expected Results: Evidence about the impact of clinical trial data sharing (in terms of re-use, published re-uses, impact of those re-uses and costs saved): Study protocols (D.ESR.2.1), SAPs (D.ESR.2.2), reports (D.ESR.2.3). Possible improvements of existing methods (publications and policy documents) (D.ESR.2.4), two research papers (D.ESR.2.5)					
Planned secondment(s): (1) Center for journalology (DM) months 23 - 34, to develop skills in journalology essential for her/his research project and to study the Ottawa data champions programme.					
Enrolment in Doctoral degree(s): UR1					

Fellow	Host institution	PhD enrolment*	Start date	Duration	Deliverables
ESR 3	Charité	Charité	Month 10	36 months	D.ESR.3.1-4
Innovative approaches to trial data anonymisation and its role for CTDS - WP 3, 5, 6					
Objectives: To investigate and develop novel methods and best practices for the anonymisation of trial data. Special emphasis will be placed on how anonymisation can be combined with additional safeguards used in CTDS platforms to maximise the usability of shared data while ensuring appropriate privacy protection for the data subjects.					
Methods: With regard to the requirements for trial data anonymisation, we will build upon important guidelines such as the requirements of the US HIPAA law and Policy 007 of the European Medicines Agency (EMA) as well as recommendations published by the Article 29 Data Protection Working Party. We plan to (1) use a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods to assess re-identification risks, and (2) consider additional safeguards, such as role-based access control, of CTDS platforms in the risk assessment and subsequent anonymisation process. An important preliminary work is ARX, an internationally successful open-source anonymization tool, which is developed by the BIH Medical Informatics Group. It will be extended with statistical procedures that can reduce risks in controlled access environments but don't provide strict guarantees on the protection level achieved. We will combine these processes with final privacy tests based on classic statistical disclosure metrics and modern machine learning-approaches to model different assumptions about the background knowledge and capabilities (modulated by the additional safeguards implemented in CTDS platforms) of an adversary aiming to de-anonymise a data-set.					
Expected Results: Evaluated tools and processes (D.ESR.3.1), case study (D.ESR.3.2), possible improvements of existing methods (software) (D.ESR.3.3), two research papers (D.ESR.3.4).					
Planned secondment(s): (1) BAYER (months 20 - 22) to learn about innovative privacy protection methods for CTDS; (2) DIFE (months 32 - 34) to learn about safeguards for CTDS implemented in the industrial context.					
Enrolment in Doctoral degree(s): Charité					

Fellow	Host institution	PhD enrollment*	Start date	Duration	Deliverables
ESR 4	Charité	Charité	Month 10	36 months	D.ESR.4.1-3
Automated screening tools for identifying data sharing, data-re-use and common reporting problems in clinical trials – WP4, 6					
Objectives: 1. To extend existing automated manuscript screening tools to detect open data deposited in clinical trial repositories with controlled access (e.g. YODA) and develop a new tool to detect re-use of clinical trial data deposited in a public repository or a repository with controlled access; 2. To develop new automated tools for detecting reporting of CONSORT elements; 3. To use these new tools to assess data sharing, data re-use and reporting quality of clinical trials, and encourage preprint authors to improve clinical trial reporting; 3. To use these tools for Meta Research studies to assess the prevalence and impact of data sharing and data re-use in clinical trials					
Expected Results: 1. Automated screening tools that will detect data sharing, data re-use, and reporting of CONSORT items in clinical trial preprints and papers (D.ESR.4.1); 2. Integration of new tools into the ScreenIT pipeline (D.ESR.4.2), which will facilitate use of these tools for Meta Research and interventions to improve data sharing, data re-use and reporting. 3. Meta Research on the prevalence and impact of data sharing and data re-use in clinical trials (Protocols and SAPs, D.ESR.4.3), two research papers (D.ESR.4.4)					
Planned secondment(s): (1) SciCrunch, months 17-21 to learn AI technology for literature reviews.					
Enrolment in Doctoral degree(s): Charité					

Fellow	Host institution	PhD enrolment*	Start date	Duration	Deliverables
ESR 5	UMG	GAU (GAUSS) UGOE	Month 10	36 months	D.ESR.5.1-4
Methodology for FAIRification, Data Enrichment and Data Sharing, WP3, 5, 6					
Objectives: To develop and evaluate methodology for improving data reusability and enriching existing data-sets with external knowledge. In this project, we assess best practice approaches for intelligent form building for better interoperability and comparability in different medical domains. Subsequent shared use of the data may benefit from linking the study-specific records with additional data from different contexts from health care or billing. Furthermore, secondary data use will require more context of the data collection and more context towards the interpretation of the data (meta-data). In this project, we examine and measure the success of record linkage and data enrichment approaches in different contexts.					

Expected Results: Evaluated toolkit (D.ESR.5.1), applied case study (D.ESR.5.2), R code/software package (D.ESR.5.3), blog/presentation (D.ESR.5.4), two research papers (D.ESR.5.5)
Planned secondment(s): (1) NFDI4Health: ZB MED, (M17-M19), to gain first-hand experience on open data and FAIR data annotation as a prerequisite for the following secondments. (2) DIfE, (M29-M31), the ESR gets practical experience with data capture, data management from primary data, questionnaire data, quality management and analyses. (3) DIfE, (M32-M34), deepening experience with actual cohorts (e.g. EPIC); to learn about complementary data types in networked clinical research.
Enrolment in Doctoral degree(s): GAU - GAUSS

Fellow	Host institution	PhD enrolment*	Start date	Duration	Deliverables
ESR 6	UPD	UPD	Month 10	36 months	D.ESR.6.1-4
Added value of meta-analyses of shared individual patient data (IPD) in mental health - WP4, 6					
Objectives: To establish the impact that IPDMA have had in the field of mental health, specifically with regards to two insofar unanswered questions: (1) Are there harms of psychological treatments, either acute (e.g. side-effects) or at a longer term (e.g. deterioration); (2) Can any prognostic factors be identified to predict response to psychological treatments or otherwise guide treatment selection? To achieve these objectives, the candidate will rely on a suite of Meta Research methods including i) a large-scale umbrella review of all IPDMA in mental health, ii) a meta-epidemiological approach to examine the role of data sharing by comparing estimates across meta-analyses from trials where investigators made data available and those where they did not and, iii) a qualitative analysis using surveys (about 2000 internet based questionnaires) and about 60 planned interviews with main authors of IPD meta-analyses to identify reasons for lack of participation, beyond what is reported in the paper.					
Expected Results: A complete collection of IPDMA in mental health (D.ESR.6.1), applied case study quantifying i) the impact of IPDMA in informing clinical practice and research in mental health (D.ESR.6.2) and ii) obstacles and systematic biases that are hindering the potential of IPDMA in this field (D.ESR.6.3), R code, extracted data, blog/presentation (D.ESR.6.3). A shiny app will be developed so that findings regarding prognostic factors and harms can be easily consulted (D.ESR.6.4), two research papers (D.ESR.1.4)					
Planned secondment(s): (1) Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, months 26 to 31, to access the largest collection of mental health IPDMA; (2) YODA, months 38-43, to learn about the process of CTDS from a respective sharing platform					
Enrolment in Doctoral degree(s): UPD					

Fellow	Host institution	PhD enrolment*	Start date	Duration	Deliverables
ESR 7	HCL	UCBL	Month 10	36 months	D.ESR.7.1-4
Towards Understanding and accepting data sharing within patients – WP4, WP6					
Objectives: To define the best practice to inform about and engage trial participants in clinical trial data sharing					
Expected Results: Survey protocol and survey questionnaire (with their translation in various languages, D.ESR.7.1); Qualitative research protocol and interview grids (with their translation in various languages, D.ESR.7.2); Analysis report (D.ESR.7.3); Recommendations on DS boundaries and on patients' information (D.ESR.7.4). The questionnaire-based survey will address about 2000 trial participants, the interviews will address about 150 persons.					
Planned secondment(s): (1) ZB MED (M14 -M16) to understand the DS technical challenges; (2) ECRIN (M29-M34) to understand how to articulate DS ethical requirements with the setting up of protocols					
Enrolment in Doctoral degree(s): University Lyon Claude Bernard					

Fellow	Host institution	PhD enrolment*	Start date	Duration	Deliverables
ESR 8	UMCU	UU	Month 10	36 months	D.ESR.8.1-4
Methodology for cross-design synthesis - WP 4, 5, 6					
Objectives: We will explore how decision making and HTA is affected by (changes in) the amount, type (e.g. non-randomised) and format (e.g. individual participant data instead of aggregate data) of available evidence. To this purpose, we will develop and evaluate statistical methodology to combine data from randomised and non-randomised studies. To help ascertaining the validity and credibility of meta-analysis results, we will develop instruments to ascertain the transparency, openness and reproducibility of evidence generated from individual data sources.					

Expected Results: Statistical methods (D.ESR.8.1), applied case study (D.ESR.8.2), R code/software package (D.ESR.8.3), blog/presentation (D.ESR.8.4), two research papers (D.ESR.8.5)
Planned secondment(s): (1) METRICS (M17-M22) to develop indicators of transparency, openness and reproducibility for clinical trials.; (2) NICE (M26-M28) Apply cross-design synthesis in a case study to study the real-world effectiveness of interventions for COVID-19. Data will be combined from published trials (aggregate data), observational studies (IPD) and patient registries (IPD). The ESR will also be externally supervised by Thomas Debray and Dalia Dawoud; (3) BAYER (M35-M37) in this collaboration, we will investigate the reproducibility of trial results across multiple (randomised and non-randomised) data sources.
Enrolment in Doctoral degree(s): The PhD student will be enrolled at Utrecht University

Fellow	Host institution	PhD enrolment*	Start date	Duration	Deliverables
ESR 9	MUW	MUW	Month 10	36 months	D.ESR.9.1-4
Using shared historic data to augment prospective clinical trials - WP3, 5, 6					
Objectives: (1) To assess and develop statistical methodology for the design and analysis of randomised clinical trials utilizing external external data sources, e.g. as external controls or for purposes of extrapolation. (2) to review current practice and reporting of the selection process of external data to augment data of randomised clinical trials. To achieve objective (1) the ESR will use analytical methods and simulation studies to develop and assess Bayesian and frequentist methods to incorporate external data in clinical trials. Objective 2 will be addressed by a systematic literature review. The potential biases introduced by the knowledge of control group data at the time of trial planning will be assessed in a simulation study as well as in a case study based on a large clinical trial data base.					
Expected Results: Trial design and analysis methods utilizing external data with a description of limitations and quantification of potential biases (D.ESR.9.1). Recommendations on bias mitigation strategies (D.ESR.9.2). Review of current practice and report on potential biases induced by the selection process of external data (D.ESR.9.3). Statistical software, case studies (D.ESR.9.4), two research papers (D.ESR.9.5).					
Planned secondment(s): 1.) Bayer (M26-M27; M38), work on a case study and corresponding analysis methods; 2.) UMCU and SDAaS (M17; M41) to work on IPD meta-analysis approaches and their potential use to incorporate external data, as, e.g., historic controls supervised by TD and VJ.					
Enrolment in Doctoral degree(s): Medical University Vienna					

Fellow	Host institution	PhD enrolment*	Start date	Duration	Deliverables
ESR 10	UZH	UZH	flexible	36 months	D.ESR.10.1-4
Evaluating outcome reporting bias in clinical trials - WP3, 6					
Objectives: Selective outcome reporting occurs when only a subset of the originally recorded outcomes of a clinical trial is reported. Outcome reporting bias (ORB) refers to the situation where the selection is influenced by the study results. For example, benefit outcomes that are non-significant and harm outcomes that are unfavourable to the treatment considered may be less likely to be reported. ORB is a serious threat to the validity of meta-analyses of both benefit ⁶⁷ and harm ⁶⁸ outcomes. Several statistical methods are available for ORB adjustments of combined treatment effect estimates based on reported summary statistics ^{69,70,71} . The availability of individual patient-level data will provide complete information on primary, secondary and harm thus enabling to assess the accuracy of meta-analytic adjustment methods in the presence of ORB through simulation. Furthermore, the extent of ORB in the medical literature will be assessed through a systematic comparison of the outcomes reported in available publications against the set of originally recorded outcomes.					
Expected Results: Neutral comparison simulation study of methods to adjust for ORB: Study protocol (D.ESR.10.1), SAP (D.ESR.10.2), report (D.ESR.10.3). Possible improvements of existing methods (Software, Publications). Systematic comparison of recorded and published outcomes (D.ESR.10.4).					

⁶⁷ Kirkham JJ, et al. (2010): The impact of outcome reporting bias in randomised controlled trials on a cohort of systematic reviews. DOI: 10.1136/bmj.c365.

⁶⁸ Saini P, et al. (2014): Selective reporting bias of harm outcomes within studies: findings from a cohort of systematic reviews. DOI: 10.1136/bmj.g6501.

⁶⁹ Kirkham JJ, et al. (2012): A multivariate meta-analysis approach for reducing the impact of outcome reporting bias in systematic reviews. DOI: 10.1002/sim.5356.

⁷⁰ Copas J, et al. (2014): A model-based correction for outcome reporting bias in meta-analysis. DOI: 10.1093/biostatistics/kxt046.

⁷¹ Copas J, et al. (2019): Model-based sensitivity analysis for outcome reporting bias in the meta analysis of benefit and harm outcomes. DOI: 10.1177/0962280217738546.

Planned secondment(s): (1) UR1 (M17-M23), development of a protocol for simulation study based on systematic literature review on ORB in clinical studies. (2) METRICS (M26-M31) Systematic comparison of the outcomes reported in available publications against the set of originally recorded outcomes. Quantitative assessment of the amount of ORB in clinical studies.
Enrolment in Doctoral degree(s): University of Zurich, Life Science Zurich Graduate School, PhD programme in Epidemiology and Biostatistics

Fellow	Host institution	PhD enrolment	Start date	Duration	Deliverables
ESR 11	UR1	UR1	flexible	36 months	D.ESR.11.1-3
Impact of clinical trial data sharing for pivotal trials in oncology – WP 4, 6					
Objectives: To assess the impact of clinical trial data sharing in terms of reproducibility of study results for pivotal trials shared by the study sponsor. This project will start with a pilot survey of all pivotal trials in oncology submitted to the European Medicine Agency and will reproduce 1) their results on the main outcome(s) and 2) all safety results. This project will develop a strategy for re-analyses and will help to pilot-test a label “reproducible science” for reproducible trials, a new form of incentive for trials sharing their data and being reproduced.					
Expected Results: Impact in terms of reproducibility of clinical data sharing in oncology trials – scoping review: Protocol (D.ESR.10.1), Report (D.ESR.10.2). First proposal of a label “reproducible science” for pivotal trials (D.ESR.10.3).					
Planned secondment(s): (1) UZH (M17 – M22) to develop skills in reproducible research practices; (2) ECRIN (M26 – M31) to learn more about policies.					
DN: UR1					

Network organisation: As presented in Figure 5, SHARE-CTD includes nine academic institutions with 11 ESRs: Eight beneficiaries will supervise 10 ESRs plus one Swiss associated partner supervising one ESR. Beneficiaries are located in six EU countries and eight EU organisations. There are further 15 (12 + 3 universities) associated partners from academics and industry.

Figure 5: Beneficiaries (grey) and associated partners (green) in SMART- CTD

Besides successful individual research projects, SHARE-CTD intends to influence the practice of CTDS for the benefit of science and society. Given the time restrictions of 48 months, the project requires a robust and efficient management structure with clear and straightforward decision-making procedures. Its backbone will be the **Management Office** (MO@LMU) with the Coordinator (CO), a Project Manager (PM) and an assistant located at the LMU. The MO@LMU is responsible for administrative, managerial, technical processes, as well as for internal and external communication.

It is closely collaborating internally with the **Supervisory Board** (SB), the individual ESRs and their supervisors, and the **Ombudsman** (OBM).

A **Selection Board** (SeB) will be set up as soon as the project is granted. It is responsible for timely recruiting and selecting ESRs. For more details see respective section below.

Three working groups (WGs) will be established to coordinate specific activities. **WG Dissemination and exploitation** (WG DE) oversees the dissemination and exploitation activities within SHARE-CTD. **WG Scientific input** (WG SI) supervises the timely completion of network-wide research tasks. **WG Public Engagement** (WG PE) coordinates the public engagement activities.

The working groups report to the SB and the **Plenary**, the MO@LMU supports their activities.

The **Plenary** comprises all members of SHARE-CTD, the ESRs, the supervisors and one representative per associated partner. The plenary meets twice per year to discuss and decide on project activities. At least one meeting will be in person when the group meets during datathons and professional training events.

The **SB** is the strategic decision-making and controlling body of the network. It reports to the plenary and needs its agreement for crucial decisions affecting the project. Details will be clarified by bylaws. The ombudsman will be elected by the plenary and will assist ESRs or any Consortium member in resolving conflicts and getting frictions harmonised, such as disputes, complaints or lack of supervision, accusations regarding scientific fraud, personal misbehaviour, which may arise during the project. The ombudsman can relay of the support of local graduate offices especially the graduate centre GC@LMU.

Thesis Advisory Committees (TAC) will supervise the individual ESR projects. The TAC report to the SB and interact with the MO@LMU as well as the WG SI. The TAC will establish the individual supervision agreements, revise the individual research plan and the individual career development plan. At least twice per year, it will monitor the ESR's progress and will intervene in case of deviations from the research and training process commonly agreed on.

The **External Advisory board (EAB)** consists of three internationally recognised experts knowledgeable about SHARE-CTD specific patient, research and training related aspects. The EAB will advise the Consortium on structure and content of training events as well as on the exposition of ESRs to academic and non-academic sectors. EAB members are: Laureen Willenberg⁷² (Patient representative), Prof. Bruno Falissard⁷³ (Trials expert), and

⁷² Patient representative, lwillenberg@gmail.com

⁷³ Université Paris-Sud, INSERM U669, Psychiatry and Biostatistics, bruno.falissard@gmail.com

Prof. Shawn Murphy⁷⁴ (Medical Informatics). The EAB interacts with the SB and the plenary.

LMU will make a “*declaration of honour*” and be responsible for dealing with the central administrative issues. Suspicion of misconduct must be immediately reported to the European Commission (EC) in written form. If the SB determines there is a case of scientific misconduct, the EC will be immediately notified and the appropriate measures will be taken. If there is any published material affected by the misconduct, it will be immediately withdrawn from publication.

Meetings of any body of the networks’ organisation will mostly use video-conferencing provided by the LMU. The plenary and SB will meet twice a year. TACs will meet at regularly with the ESR (at least twice a year). Working groups will meet at least quarterly.

Figure 6 represents the planned network structure.

Progress monitoring and evaluation of individual projects: During the meeting *Kick-off propaedeutic training* (month 10) each ESRs and her/his TAC members initiate a *career development plan* (CDP) that calibrates research interests between ESRs and supervisors, matches individual career perspectives with the offered programme content (training, secondments), brings expectations on both sides on an equal footing. Each individual CDP is the starting point for the ESR’s roadmap through the programme. It will be reviewed and updated by the ESR, her/his TAC and the SB. It accompanies the ESR’s individual research plan (RP). Each ESR poses duties regarding research, training, as well as practical milestones that need harmonisation and continuous adjustment.

Figure 6: Network Organisation

Each ESR will have her/his Thesis Advisory Committee (TAC) composed of two local supervisors (one from a complementary discipline) and at least one joint supervisor from another SHARE-CTD partner. The TAC sets up and maintains the individual CDP. The

⁷⁴ Professor of Neurology and Biomedical Informatics at Harvard Medical School, Chief Research Information Officer at Mass General Brigham, SNMURPHY@PARTNERS.ORG

TAC supports the ESR to develop her/his research plan (RP) detailing objectives, methods, milestones and deadlines. Supervisors at the host institution will hold regular meetings (twice a month) with the ESRs to discuss issues regarding research, training, and time management. The TAC will monitor ESR's progress (regarding the ESR specific deliverables) as frequent as necessary (at least twice a year) and report the meeting minutes and updated CDPs and RPs to the SB. The SB will evaluate the overall role of the ongoing individual ESR project regarding the general SHARE-CTD perspective and will give feedback.

There is the offer by the LMU Graduate Centre for supervision and input to solve problems. The LMU Graduate Centre is also interested to install a quantitative research project on the SHARE-CTD supervision process.

Risk management at consortium level: The SB will regularly monitor the progress of the project (milestones). Any alterations to the research programme will be agreed on by the SB and communicated via MO@LMU to the Project Officer of the REA and request formal authorisation. SHARE-CTD implements a consensus-driven decision making that ensures fulfilment of SHARE-CTD objectives. The Consortium is expected to facilitate response in case of contingencies. For example, a new epidemic outbreak can be handled by intensive use of already established video conferencing tools. Risk assessment will be undertaken by the SB and discussed at the plenary meetings; risk evaluation and proposed mitigation measures will be included in the annual report to the EC.

A specific risk on the consortium level is *social instability*. It is related to mental health issues and productivity of individual ESRs. To this end, all persons involved in running network events will receive training in moderation techniques (offered by the Graduate Centre @ LMU during the kick-off meeting) for facilitating a safe, balanced and inclusive discussion. ESRs will be encouraged to form an early career researcher group to socialise and privately share experiences and concerns. This safe space will minimise the impact of power dynamics by allowing ESRs to raise any concerns as a group.

The network will organise a journal club series focused on diversity, equity and inclusion both in science, and in clinical trial design and conduct. This highly interactive format will encourage discussion, skill development, role-playing and other exercises to practice new skills. Each PI/ESR pair will organise one session/year, and all PIs and ESRs will be required to attend at least six sessions/year. If an external speaker is invited, the PI and ESRs must both be actively involved in moderating the discussion. At least one session per year will be organised in collaboration with the patient advocate on the advisory board. Issues to be discussed will include power dynamics, systematic factors that adversely affect the scientific careers and mental health of members of underrepresented groups, practicing allyship, anti-racism and whiteness in science, including patients from underrepresented minorities in clinical trials, issues related to global collaborations and responsible conduct of clinical trials in low- and middle-income countries, and patient and stakeholder engagement.

Supervisory board: Membership will be composed of one representative from each beneficiary and partner organisation, and three representatives from the ESRs. Gender balance in the board's composition is strived for. All members will participate in discussions and will have voting rights in decisions. Decisions will only be made if two-thirds of the SB are present or represented and will be taken by a two thirds majority. The decision-making process is set out in detail in the Consortium Agreement and bylaws. Each member in the SB has a term of one year and is elected by the plenary. TACs report to the SB, The SB will discuss the work of each individual ESR and her/his career development plan, the quality of the training programme of SHARE-CTD and debate an adequate balance – for

each ESR – between scientific knowledge courses, the training through the individual research projects and transferable skills training. The SB will reflect back to each TAC the results of the internal discussion.

The SB will oversee the processes related to and the completions of milestones. Non-academic partners in the SB will ensure that the ESRs training fulfils the needs of both academic and the non-academic sector and therefore to enhance their intersectoral employability. The SB will facilitate an active and continuous communication and exchange of best practice among Consortium members to maximise the synergies of the network.

Recruitment strategy is defined by the Selection Board (SeB). The SeB will be established as soon as possible after the start of the project and is active during its first year. It consists of future local TAC members from beneficiaries and the Swiss associated partner. The SeB organises the recruitment process (tailored to the type of positions advertised) as open, efficient, transparent, gender-balanced, supportive and internationally comparable. This process follows the Code of Conduct for Recruitment of Researchers in the European Charter for Researchers⁷⁵ (CCRR). Advertisements will provide an attractive and broad description of knowledge and competencies required together with a description of the employer and the working environment. The members of the SeB bring the needed expertise and competences (see Section 1.4 in part B1) to define the recruitment strategy and selection process. The selection process will be based on recommendation letters as well as interviews with the ESR candidates considering merit, potential, and which matches researcher's background to ESR position requirements. To allow a fair selection process, the SeB will create a list of selection criteria and will train all persons involved in the selection process. Here the Graduate Centre of the LMU offers practical support in all preparations and proposed training.

SHARE-CTD tries to recruit ESRs during the first 6 months of the project. ESR projects and locations as well as working conditions and entitlements, including career development prospects will be in detailed described on the project website. Platforms used to advertise positions will include: European Researcher Mobility Portal (EURAXESS, <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/>), Marie-Curie Fellowship Association website, Consortium member's webpages, LinkedIn, Research Gate, as well as regional relevant platforms such as Academics. We will also use the websites of scientific societies whose field of activities touch or overlap with SHARE-CTD intentions.

An online application tool (provided by the LMU) will be used and realistic application deadlines set. The tool includes modules to collect standard information and an additional module will be customised to the formal requirements of Marie Curie actions. Applicants will be asked to give their three, prioritised, preferences for the ESR projects listed in the advertisement. After a first assessment, suitable candidates will be invited to a job interview at the hosting institution – either by video conferencing or face-to-face. The final selection of ESRs is the responsibility of each beneficiary with the endorsement of the SeB.

A specific criterion will be the ESR's potential to interact with the different SHARE-CTD partners and to live the envisioned interdependences between projects and SHARE-CTD activities. Each hosting institution will be responsible for the administrative procedures for hiring the selected ESRs and ensuring signed contracts by month 9.

⁷⁵ <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/charter> [10.11.2022].

There will be ongoing interaction between the three working groups (Dissemination, Scientific Input, Public engagement) and the ESRs in order to develop material to deliverables (D3.3, D4.3, D5.4 - D5.6, D6.2 - D6.4) and contributions to social media.

In case of growing conflicts between ESR and supervisor, the ombudsman may mediate between both parties (if needed with the support of the Graduate Centre @LMU).

Summarising, there is a narrow grid of feedback and monitoring channels into the ESR's development, which allows early detection and intervention in case of impending dangers that imply severe deviation from the commonly agreed CDP. The individual participation at the training programme (schooling, datathon, and professional training) is closely monitored by the MO@LMU and feedback is immediately given to the ESR and TAC.

Gender aspects: The structure of the consortium is not well-balanced regarding sex. SHARE-CTD has four females and seven male PIs. The selection of ESRs will be gender balanced following the EU Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of researchers as laid down in the European Charter for Researchers. All ESR positions will be openly advertised. Advertisements will include an explicit statement that members of groups who are underrepresented in science are encouraged to apply. This may include women, racial and ethnic minorities, persons with disabilities, applicants from low- or middle-income countries, or applicants who are diverse with regards to gender or sexual orientation. We aim to ensure that half of the ESRs enrolled in the network are women, and at least one third are diverse in other aspects. PIs, ESRs, network partners, advisory board members and others who attend network events will be required to adhere to a code of conduct. Code of conduct concerns will be directed to the ombudsman. If a complaint involves a SB member, that person will be replaced by another person until the issue is resolved, or for the remainder of his or her term, at the discretion of the committee.

Environmental aspects in light of the [MSCA Green Charter](#)⁷⁶: Researcher related measures are the use of video conferencing tool for communication (provided for organisational meetings, schooling events, and individual intra network communication). Datathons will be partially organised as group meetings. The geographic distributions of partners allow to travel by train if personal meetings are considered. Meeting places will be chosen to minimise the travel distance. All project related events where physical attendance is necessary (propaedeutic, three datathons, closing conference) are organised as sustainably as possible. We will support ESRs in developing greater awareness on environmental sustainability and green computing (part of teaching events).

4.2 Quality, capacity and role of each participant, including hosting arrangements and extent to which the consortium as a whole brings together the necessary expertise

Appropriateness of the infrastructure and capacity of each participating organisation: The participating organisation supervising the ESRs are high level academic research and teaching institutions with established infrastructures (PhD programmes, active research environments, international networks): LMU, UR1, Charité,

⁷⁶ The MSCA Green Charter constitutes a code of good practice for all recipients of MSCA funding – both individuals and institutions – and promotes the mainstreaming of environmental considerations in all aspects of project implementation. In so doing, the Charter seeks to reduce the environmental footprint of MSCA-funded projects, to raise awareness of environmental sustainability, and to serve as a catalyst in promoting best practice in sustainable research management.

UMG (+UGOE), UPD, HCL (+UCBL), MUW, UMCU (+UU), and UZH. In case of UMG, HCL, and UMCU, the medical centre is accompanied by the respective university that grants the PhD (UGOE, UCBL, and UU). All universities involved have facilities to support graduate work (Infrastructure for application processes, training facilities for supervisors, training for ESRs, research activities on the efficiency of the PhD processes in respective faculties, mediation facilities for conflicts, technical infrastructure, research infrastructure). They will be supportive.

The academic institutions are complemented by 12 associated partners from industry (Bayer, SCr, SDAaS), public institutions (NICE, ECRIN, ZB MED) and research organisations (METRICS, YODA, CFJ, DIFe, VUA, LORIER). These associated partners provide a wide range of needed competencies, activities, and opportunities that stimulate the research of our ESRs and point the way to an appropriate employment field for them. Our associated partners are imbedded in large infrastructures guaranteeing the needed functionalities within the network. Since CTDS is a fast-developing field in industry as well as in academia, the associated partners are highly motivated to interact within this network. All partners will be involved in teaching. They will also provide opportunities for a total of 23 secondments comprising a total of 102 months. The secondments are closely linked to the research tasks of the ESRs. Figure 5 gives an overview on beneficiaries and associated partners.

Consortium composition and exploitation of participating organisations'

complementarities: There are several complementarities: Research/Practice; data provider/ data user; best practice/impact; academic/non-academic sectors; researchers/public; technical tools / methodology; practice / regulations; ethics / technology; privacy / public interest. SHARE-CTD looks at processes how to prepare data for sharing [Bayer, YODA, ECRIN are data provider as well as NICE, DIFe, and ZB MED] and how to use shared data (by scientists in academia [LMU, UZH, MUW, UMCU], regulatory bodies [NICE], and industry [Bayer, SDAaS]). They need respective instruments and methodology [ZB MED, UMG, Charité] and guidance [ECRIN, METRICS, CFJ]. SHARE-CTD looks on best practices, especially on available processes and tools [Charité, UMG, ZB MED, DIFE, ECRIN] that need improvement by new methodology [LMU, Charité, MUV, UMCU, SDAaS, SCr]. It also develops and applies instruments to measure impact: By Meta Research on the practice of CTDS [METRICS, UR1, UPD, VUA] as well as how it is reflected in the literature [CFJ, SCr, UR1]. It is also relevant to reflect the position of the subject whose data is shared [HCL, UPD]. SHARE-CTD will maintain a discussion on the relationship between ethical / privacy related issues and issues of a more efficient data usage to create scientific value. The composition of the consortium is well suited to bring different points of view together: Research, teaching, and practice provides an interference of diverse partners within SHARE-CTD. Cooperation between industry, regulators and the network gains interest by the growing need to hire experts who understand the complex process of CTDS, to optimise this process, and to provide best practice.

Commitment of beneficiaries and associated partners to the programme:

As mentioned above, the associated partners offer a total of 23 opportunities for research-oriented secondments comprising a total of 102 months. They are instrumental in the ESR training in the fields of clinical trial regulation, trial related medical information processing, practical CTDS, fields of relevant CTDS, and professional training. All associated partners (Bayer, SCr, NICE, ECRIN, ZB MED, METRICS, YODA, CFJ, DIFE, and SDAaS) also contribute to the training. Detailed plans can only be made after approval of the application.

5 ETHICS ISSUES

The SHARE-CTDS project will work on innovative approaches for clinical trial data sharing. Data from clinical trials is personal and subject to data protection laws having important privacy, security and ethical implications that the SHARE-CTDS project will address explicitly and robustly in full compliance with relevant legislation. In each work package and task we will comply with national legal, ethical and ethics committee requirements regarding our specific engagement in the secondary use of clinical trials data. The data providing partners have already established trial data sharing platforms and we will sign data use agreements after assessing legal and ethical legitimacy of our planned uses of data and implement all information security and data protection measures required by the data sharing partner. Consent may be required from individuals as part of the interviews and evaluation studies to be performed, which will be coordinated with the local ethics committees of the participating sites. Any signed and dated declaration of informed consent will remain at the investigators' site and will be safely archived by the investigator so that the forms can be retrieved at any time for monitoring, auditing and inspection purposes. The informed consent forms (ICFs) will incorporate wording that complies with relevant data protection and privacy legislation. Ethics committees ensure that the collection, processing and use of data does not disproportionately compromise the integrity and self-determination of individuals and according applications will be submitted.

The collection, exchange, and processing of personal data will be performed taking full account of the principles of privacy and data protection and with minimal risk of the individual's privacy. All partners will follow the requirements of the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR 2016/679). Personal data of study participants processed during re-analyses will be protected, in compliance with the requirements of the GDPR. Partners will keep on file a declaration of compliance or authorization for processing personal data if it is required under national law. If no declaration of compliance or authorization is required under the applicable national law, a statement from the designated Data Protection Officer that all personal data processing is carried out according to European and national legislation will be kept on file.

All project activities will be carried out involving a constant ethics and regulatory monitoring process in order to ensure transparency, fairness, and respect for individuals' fundamental rights, in compliance with the current regulations. The SHARE-CTDS project will adopt a specific ethically-focused approach during the development, deployment, and evaluation of AI-based methods, taking into consideration the Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) in each phase of the project implementation. The consortium will guarantee the following principles as described in the ALTAI: human agency and oversight; privacy and data governance; transparency; fairness, diversity and non-discrimination; societal and environmental well-being; accountability.

ESR1 will use data from different trial data sharing platforms;

ESR2 will use data derived from published articles and will analyse it with AI, no personal data will be involved;

ESR3 will develop AI to protect personality rights of patients who participate in clinical trial. The project will work with data sets from clinical trials;

ESR4 will develop and test AI to extract information from scientific medical documents, this does not involve personal data;

ESR5 will study strategies to make clinical trial data "fair" and will work with sets from clinical trials;

ESR6 will do meta-research on the use of individual patient data for meta-analyses in mental health. The project will work with data sets from clinical trials;

ESR7 will perform survey and interviews;
ESR8 will use data from clinical trials for methodological research;
ESR9 will use data from clinical trials for methodological research;
ESR10 will use data from clinical trials for methodological research.

As mentioned above, all project will ask for IRB review and approval.